

Review Article

When Will Science Finally Accept "G-D's Physics" As the New Twenty-First Century Physics Paradigm?!

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Note: Dr. Bentovish is calling Astronomers & Cosmologists to collaborate directly with him to further validate the "Seven Months UNCIARE-JRH Validation Challenge" which will provide an unequivocal support for "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) New 21st Century Scientific Paradigm! Dr. Bentovish (Bentwich) e-mail is: drbentwich@gmail.com

Abstract

Due to a major "Paradigmatic Crisis" of the Old "Material-Causal-Random" Paradigm of Twentieth Century General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) as signified by a fundamental "theoretical inconsistency" between its two primary "pillars", e.g., General Relativity Theory (GRT) & Quantum Mechanics (QM), and its principle inability to account for the "Hubble Tension's" increase in the universe's rate of expansion – from its initial (early-stage) Cosmological Measurements to the current Astronomical Measure value (e.g., assumed to be accounted for by purely hypothetical & undetected "Dark-Matter" [DM] comprising up to 95% of all the mass in the universe?!). In this (seminal) article The New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm" is being tested based on direct empirical validations of two of its unique "Critical Predictions": associated with a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" postulate predicted "Non-Continuous Increase in the Universe's Expansion Rate" (UNCIARE) during the "Jewish Rosh-Hashana" (two days special time interval), and the "Proton Radius Puzzle" findings; **Based on direct empirical evidence validating these two unique "G-D's Physics" Critical Predictions (e.g., more valid than corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM) "G-D's Physics" must be accepted as the New (valid) Twenty-First Century Physics Paradigm!** An additional "G-D's Physics' Seven Months' Challenge (for Astronomers all of the world!) is called for: to further "G-d's Physics" precise UNCIARE-JRH's increase in the current Astronomical Measure of the universe's expansion rate (i.e., to be measured during the next seven months at an accuracy level of $0.000968 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$) by a **"Minute Annual Increase" (MAI) of $0.000968 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$; that will occur on the next JRH, on Oct. 3rd-4th, 2024 (and carry on until the next JRH: Sep. 22nd-23rd, 2025 – in which another MAI of $0.000968 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$ will be added to the universe's accelerated rate of expansion!)** To the extent that this specific "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH MAI (of $0.000968 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$) will be validated empirically then this will unequivocally validate "G-D's Physics" whole new theoretical model, alongside its emphasis of the centrality of the CHCF (JRH), and the actual Cosmological age of the universe! It would also further substantiate "G-D's Physics" postulated existence of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (at the "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") and which has "pre-planned" (and is continuously "executing"- and "adjusting") the development of the whole universe from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State"; in which Science & Humanity will recognize the singularity of this UCP, alongside its "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" & "Harmony" (e.g., bound to affect Humanity's existence and behavior – with Physics' Scientific Community's current inevitable acceptance of "G-D's Physics" New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm)!

Introduction

The mandate given to Science (by Humanity) is to investigate the true nature of the physical reality -based on stringent methodologies and tools that combine between obtaining replicable data (in any given scientific sub-discipline) and applying logical and mathematical inference tools to determine the true nature of the physical reality! It is also a well-known fact that any such sub-discipline of Science evolves based on an alteration between phases of a given "Standard Paradigm", in which the scientific investigation (in that given discipline) adheres to the basic "assumptions" and "laws" of such "Standard Paradigm"; which then reaches a state of a "Paradigmatic-Crisis", e.g., in which there exist: a) Basic "theoretical-inconsistencies" between the foundations of that "Standard Paradigm". b) inability of that Standard Paradigm to explain a certain major phenomenon;

Indeed, according to Thomas Kuhn's (1962) in-depth (acceptable) analysis of the "Structure of Scientific Revolutions", whenever a given scientific discipline reaches such a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" state, this inevitable must lead to the discovery of a "New Scientific Paradigm", which can satisfy a series of "stringent scientific criteria" in order to be accepted by the Scientific Community as the new valid Scientific Paradigm (e.g., replacing and transcending the Old "Standard Paradigm"):

A "case study" demonstrating Kuhn's precise description of the "Structure of Scientific Revolutions" can indeed be taken from Einstein's "overturning" of the Old Newtonian Mechanical (Standard Paradigm) in favor of the NSP of GRT:

a) There existed a basic "Theoretical Inconsistency" between the

Old Standard Paradigm of Newtonian Mechanics and Maxwellian Electromagnetic Theory.

b) There also existed a "Major Unexplained Phenomenon" relating to the purely hypothetical "Ether" concept which was assumed to permeate the entire physical universe (and was necessary for Newtonian Mechanics), but yet could not be detected experimentally despite numerous experiments aimed at detecting this "elusive Ether" concept?!

c) Einstein's Special & General Relativity Theory was shown capable of resolving this apparent "Theoretical Inconsistency" between Newtonian Classical Mechanics and Maxwellian Electromagnetic Theory;

d) GRT also "discarded" this purely hypothetical "Ether" concept – as "superfluous" (i.e., "non-existent") based on the broader theoretical framework of GRT!

e) Most importantly, GRT was able to identify- and empirically validate- a unique "Critical Prediction", e.g., regarding the "double-valued" curvature of Mercury's Perihelion pathway (around the Sun – due to GRT's discovered "curvature of Space-Time" by massive objects!); as more valid than Newtonian Mechanics's corresponding prediction (i.e., 0.8 ARC according to Newtonian Mechanical prediction – as opposed to the empirically validated Einsteinian GRT's 1.6 ARC, verified empirically through Eddington's well-known 1919 Solar Eclipse measurements)!

It is true to say that according to Kuhn's (brilliant) analysis of this 'Structure of Scientific Revolutions' – that even when all of these stringent scientific criteria have been satisfied (completely) by the NSP: "Sociologically", it may still be difficult for some scientists to accept- adapt-and shift- their scientific investigation towards the inevitable need to accept and "operate" based on this NSP (e.g., due to the fact that these scientists have been "accustomed" and "acquainted" to the Old "Standard Paradigm" – which is proven to be too "limited" and which must "give way" to the empirically validated NSP)!? But, one thing is clear, i.e., even according to Kuhn's (Sociological) analysis of the 'Structure of Scientific Revolutions': that is, that it is inevitable that Science must "grow"- "adjust"- and "embrace"- this empirically validated NSP as the New Scientific Paradigm (which replaces the Old "Standard Paradigm"), because at the end of the day, Science must follow the basic mandate that it received from Humanity at large) in order to justify its unique status as providing Humanity with the trusted analysis of the true nature of the physical reality!?

Therefore, Science must adhere to- and follow precisely- its own basic methodology and stringent criteria for testing and validating any NSP – when it is clear that any given scientific discipline has reached such a state of a "Paradigmatic Crisis", which necessitates a diligent analysis and empirical testing (and validation) of any candidate NSP! This was indeed the case with Einstein's General Relativity Theory (GRT): when it was clear that Newtonian Mechanics (and Maxwellian Electromagnetic Theory) have reached such a state of a "Paradigmatic Crisis" (signified by: a) the basic "theoretical-inconsistency" between Newtonian Mechanics and Maxwellian Electromagnetic Theory. b) principle inability of this Old "Standard Classical Mechanics Paradigm" to account for the existence of a purely hypothetical "ether" concept, which was supposed to permeate the whole universe as a "medium" for the transmission of electromagnetic light signals – but which could not be detected despite numerous attempts to do so?! Then, Einstein's General (and Special) Theory of Relativity, shown capable of resolving this apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between Newtonian Mechanics and Electromagnetic Theory by expanding the basic theoretical understanding of the true nature of the universe, and the physical laws governing it) became a leading "candidate" as the New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century! At this point, Einstein called leading Astronomers to carry out a ("time-sensitive") empirical testing of his (unique) "Critical Prediction" regarding Mercury's "double-valued" perihelion curvature around the Sun (e.g., 1.6 ARC relative to 0.8 ARC as predicted by Newtonian Classical Mechanics) due to GRT's assumed curvature of "Space-Time" by the mass of the Sun! Fortunately, Eddington (alongside two other Astronomical Measurements Expeditions) set to verify Einstein's "bold" unique "Critical Predictions – specifically during the 1919 ("time-sensitive") Solar Eclipse event, which indeed resulted in Ed-

dington's precise validation of Einstein's unique "double-valued" 1.6 ARC measurement! Remarkably, despite the (abovementioned "Sociological") "resistance" of certain scientists to accept the inevitable conclusion where-in Einstein's empirically validated GRT unique "double-valued" "Critical Prediction" measurement – must therefore be accepted as the "New Scientific Paradigm" (NSP) for Twenty-First Century Physics, GRT eventually did "triumph" over Newtonian Mechanics as the new acceptable 21st Century Physics Paradigm!

We now stand at a precisely (equivalent) "Historic Scientific Turning-Point"! The Old "Material-Causal-Ransom" (MCR) "Standard Paradigm" has reached a clear "Paradigmatic Crisis", signified by:

A. There exists a basic "Theoretical Inconsistency" between GRT & QM!

This "Theoretical Inconsistency" stems from GRT's insistence upon the "Speed of Light Barrier" (SLB) limiting the passage of any signal (or even information) across space and time; as opposed to the empirically validated "Quantum Entanglement" phenomenon, which indicates that a measurement of one "entangled particle" "instantaneously" determines the "complementary value" of the "other" "entangled particle" (e.g., even if they are separated by a distance greater than can be traversed by a light signal), which seems to "violate" or "negate" GRT's SLB!?

B. The Existence of a Major "Unexplained" "Hubble-Tension" Phenomenon & Associated Purely Hypothetical "Dark-Matter" & "Dark-Energy" (DM/DE) Concepts?!

The "Major Unexplained Phenomenon" which cannot be accounted for by the Old MCR of GRT & QM are the purely hypothetical "DM/DE" concepts – which are assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass and energy in the universe, but which cannot yet be detected despite over twenty years of intensive experimental attempts to do so?! As known the whole reason for hypothesizing the existence of these purely hypothetical "DM/DE" concepts – is the empirically validated accelerated expansion of the universe, i.e.: The "**Hubble Tension**" (Verde et al., 2023): there exists an "unexplained gap" between the earlier Cosmological measurements of the universe's expansion rate, and the higher contemporary measurements of an increased rate of the universe's expansion rate?! The current Astronomical Measurements of the universe's expansion rate is found to be: $H_0 = 73.0 \pm 1.0 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$ (SH0ES Collaboration; Riess et al. 2022); as opposed to the significantly lower rate of the universe's expansion obtained from an analysis of Planck observations of the cosmic microwave background (Planck Collaboration et al. 2020), predicting $H_0 = 67.4 \pm 0.5 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ together with the Λ CDM Model?!

The intriguing point is that even beyond the "troubling" fact that those purely hypothetical "DM/DE" concepts could not be verified experimentally (for the past twenty years)!? those purely hypothetical DM/DE concepts – may only be relevant for the (first) Hubble's Law, but not for the (second) "Hubble Tension" phenomenon. This is because even if (somehow) these purely hypothetical DM/DE concepts existed they could not explain an increase (over time) in the rate of the universe's expansion! Rather, even if (somehow) there existed this "mysterious" and "elusive" DM/DE concepts, they could only account for a "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion (e.g., which does not change over time) – but not for the "Hubble Tension" validated "enigma" indicating an "unexplained" increase in the universe's expansion rate from its early Cosmological Measurement to the current (significantly increased) Astronomical measurement rate of expansion over time?! Therefore, it is clear that the purely hypothetical stance of those DM/DE concepts (e.g., which could not be validated experimentally for over two full decades of intensive experimental efforts to do so?!), alongside its inability to account for the "**Hubble Tension**" enigma point at the "Paradigmatic Crisis" of the Old MCR Paradigm (together with the abovementioned "Theoretical Inconsistency" between GRT & QM)!

C. The New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm has been shown capable of resolving this GRT-QM Theoretical Inconsistency!

Indeed, the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm has been shown capable of resolving the apparent "Theoretical Inconsistency" between GRT & QM based on the discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) that simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels' four (basic) Physical Features (e.g., of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") at the "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{-50}$ sec!" thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frame/s" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every "minimal time-point"!

Perhaps the key unresolved "enigma" in Twenty-First Century's Theoretical Physics is the "Gravitational Enigma" (GE), i.e.: *Deciphering the underlying mechanism responsible for the phenomenon of "gravitation" which can:* a) *Unify between General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM); and b) Offer an alternative satisfactory explanation for the universe's accelerated rate of expansion that is not based on the purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" (DM) concept (which is assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe but could not be detected even after two full decades of intensive experimentation?!); c) Unify between the Gravitational Force and the other Three Forces (e.g., Strong- & Weak- Nuclear Forces and the Electromagnetic Force!); d) Offer an alternative theoretical explanation for the "curvature of Space-Time" by "massive objects" (e.g., based on the G-D'S PHYSICS' New Scientific "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm);* Thus far, the "Gravitational Force" has been explained based on GRT's key assumption wherein this "Gravitational Force" (GF) is responsible for the "curvature of Space-Time" – i.e., without actually explaining its underlying "nature". Moreover, this assumed GF remains "inexplicable" (and "independent") of the Standard Model's proven capacity to unify between those other Three Forces, based on the discovery of elementary subatomic particles' interactions, and therefore is seen an unresolved "Gravitational Enigma"?! The purpose of this article is to try and offer an alternative solution for this "Gravitational Enigma" (GE) based on the discovery of a New "G-d's Physics" Scientific Paradigm [1-30].

The potential capacity of this New G-D'S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm to resolve this "Gravitational Enigma" (GE) stems from its discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{-50}$ sec!"), thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every "minimal time-point"! Additionally, the UCP's simultaneous computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel (in the universe) across a series of (such) UF's frame/s yields the UCP's novel "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" (for each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe) – as being computed by this singular UCP, based on its two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" and "Consistency! According to this (new) G-D'S PHYSICS explanation, the UCP (simultaneously) computes these four basic physical features – including the "mass" value of each exhaustive spatial pixel (in the universe) based on the four possible combinations of those "Framework" (e.g., "frame" or "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" or "inconsistent") "Computational Dimensions": Such that the UCP computes "Framework" – "consistent" vs. "inconsistent" computations, as the "space" and "energy" values of any given spatial pixel (across a given series of UF's); and "Object" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" computations, as the "mass" and "time" values (across a given UF's series) (Figure 1):

FIGURE 1: UCP'S COMPUTATION OF FOUR PHYSICAL FEATURES

Framework/Consist.	Frame	Object
Consistent	"Space"	"Mass"
Inconsistent	"Energy"	"Time"

Intriguingly, these novel "G-D'S PHYSICS" UCP's "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features also led to the discovery of an "Universal Computational Formula" (Figure 2), which was shown to completely integrate these four basic physical features as secondary computational "by-products" of this singular (higher-ordered) UCP (for the first time in Physics)!

FIGURE 2: The "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF)

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} c^2 \\ h \end{array} \right\} = \frac{s * e}{t * m}$$

UF's { $\tau \dots \mu \dots \kappa$ } [PxI (a...z)]

Note: which is accompanied by "G-D'S PHYSICS" computational (above) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time".

The UCF's Relativistic Format:

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} E * s \\ t \end{array} \right\} = \frac{M * c^2}{h}$$

in which GRT's (famous) "Energy-Mass Equivalence" is embedded within the UCF.

The UCF's Quantum Format:

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} t * m \\ s * e \end{array} \right\} = \frac{h * c^2}{c^2}$$

in which "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's" ("complimentary pairs")

are embedded as "special cases" within the UCF (see previously elaborated analysis of "G-D'S PHYSICS" or G-D'S PHYSICS).

Significantly, the first (abovementioned) facet of this New G-D'S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm's potential resolution of the GE's first component – i.e., a) Deciphering the underlying mechanism responsible for the phenomenon of "gravitation" which can both unify between General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM); is given through this (singular higher-ordered) UCP's (in-depth) analysis of the (true) "computational basis" of the "theoretical-inconsistency" between GRT & QM stems: According to the New G-D'S PHYSICS's computational analysis, this "GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency" stems from GRT's strict "Speed of Light Barrier" for the transmission of any "signal" (or even "information") across "space" and "time" – which seems to be "contradicted" by QM's "Quantum Entanglement Phenomenon", indicating that the measurement of one "entangled particle" "instantaneously" affects the "complimentary" ("space/energy" or "mass/time") measurement of the other "entangled particle"?! But, according to the new CUT's Paradigm, the (alternative) explanation- and "resolution"- of this apparent "GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency" stems from the UCP's singular (higher-ordered simultaneous) computation of all "Single Spatial-Temporal" computation ("SST"): "particle" of relativistic "object" (e.g., relating to only "one" spatial-temporal point, at any given moment), "Multi Spatial-Temporal" computation (MST): "wave" (e.g., relating to at least "two" points being measured at any point in time) or "Exhaustive Spatial Temporal" (EST) computation (e.g., relating to all "exhaustive" spatial pixels comprising an entire "Universal Frame", UF), across a series of UF's frames (Figure 3);

FIGURE 3: UCP'S "SST", "MST" & "EST" COMPUTATIONS

UCP's Computations	SST	MST	EST
Num. "ST" Points	1	2+	All Points

D. Two Unique "Critical Predictions" Differentiating "G-D's Physics" From GRT's & QM's Predictions!

Based upon "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, it identified two unique "Critical Predictions" that clearly differentiate it from the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM, as detailed below; Indeed, to the extent that these unique "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" would be validated as more accurate than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM, then "G-D's Physics" will have to be accepted by the Scientific Community as the New (satisfactory) Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century!

Taken together, this shown capability of "G-D's Physics" to resolve the basic "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM, and also offer a (satisfactory) alternative explanation for the (otherwise "unexplained") "UNCIARE" (or as it been termed recently as the "Hubble Tension") increase in the universe's measured accelerated rate of expansion – this positions "G-D's Physics" as a leading candidate to be accepted by the Scientific Community as the New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century Physics! We are therefore led to the inevitable conclusion wherein – **if at least one (of the two below mentioned unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" will be verified (in the Results section), then Science must accept "G-D's Physics" as the New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics!**

Methods & Results

In order to directly contrast between the New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal"

Paradigm, "G-d's Physics" identified a unique "Critical-Prediction" stemming from its new "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on the UCP's singular higher-ordered two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" (frame/object) and "Consistency" (consistent/inconsistent): According to this new UCP's Computational Dimensions definition of the "mass" of any given particle as an "object-consistent" computational measure:

$$M: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)]= O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i\dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical): such that:

$$M: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i\dots n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value."G-d's Physics" unique "Critical-Prediction" predicts that relatively "more-massive" particles such as the (negatively charged) "Muon" would be measured as more "spatially-consistent" than an equivalently (negatively charged) "electron" particle! This unique "G-d's Physics" "Critical-Prediction" was de-facto tested by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" associated experiments conducted by Pohl et al. (2010) :

The "Proton-Radius Puzzle" Confirms "G-D's Physics" Critical Prediction

Pohl et al. (2010) set to measure the radius of a Hydrogen Proton – contrasting between the Standard Hydrogen surrounded by the (negatively charged) electron, and a "Muonic Hydrogen" in which its electron was replaced by a much more massive (negatively charged) "Muon" particle; Surprisingly, they found that the Proton radius was greatly decreased in the Muonic-Hydrogen, than in the Standard Hydrogen – which they termed as the "Proton-Radius Puzzle", because it could not be satisfactorily accounted for by Relativistic or Quantum Models?! In contrast, these findings conform and validate the unique "Critical-Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm stemming from its abovementioned new UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given subatomic particle:

$$M: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)]= O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i\dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical). This is because according to the New "G-d's Physics" UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given subatomic particle, a more massive a particle possesses more "spatially-consistent" physical features – therefore predicting the "Critical-Prediction" of the relatively "more-massive" Muonic Hydrogen Proton possessing a more "spatially-consistent", i.e., smaller and more accurate, than the relatively "less-massive" electron-associated Standard Hydrogen Proton measurements! Noteworthy is the fact that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm regarding the more "spatially-consistent" measurements of the relatively more massive "Muon-Hydrogen" as opposed to the relatively less-massive "electron-Hydrogen" – could not be accounted for by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of RT & QM (e.g., despite various attempts to explain this "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings: the "three-body force" (Karr & Hilico, 2012), interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction, (Onofrio, 2013; Zyga, 2013), higher dimension gravity, (Dahia, & Lemos,,

2016), a new boson, (McKeen & Miller, 2016) and the quasi-free hypothesis $\pi+$ (Lestone, 2017); and therefore constitutes a direct empirical validation of this New "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm!

The "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG) Confirms "G-D's Physics" "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Another means for testing a unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm relates to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE) due to the Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) associated with the two days' "Rosh-Hashanah" time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCR/UCP; In contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts' ensuing "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion acceleration – which should not increase with time! Based on the New "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" which assumes that the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion undergoes a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion", at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashanah" two days' special time-interval! An indirect empirical validation of this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm was already given based on the unexplained findings regarding the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG)!

Empirically, a basic (unexplained) "gap" exists between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion (Scolnic et al. 2014; Riess et al. 2018a, 2019; Shajib et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2020)?! This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) negates the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumption of the existence of (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts as "causing" the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion; because even if such (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" concepts existed (e.g., which failed to be detected after two decades of experimentation), according to the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm they could not interact (directly or indirectly) with any constituting element of the universe "causing" it to accelerate the rate of the universe's expansion! Therefore, they could not result in the observed CAAEG "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Therefore, the abovementioned results unequivocally validate and support two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM: as indicated by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings, and by the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap"! In this respect (as stated above), we now stand at an equivalent "historic juncture" to Eddington's 1919 Solar Eclipse empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" regarding Mercury's double-valued Perihelion curvature around the Sun – which validated Einstein's GRT as more valid than the Older Newtonian Mechanics Paradigm. ***Therefore, we are led to the unequivocal conclusion wherein "G-D's Physics" must be accepted as the New Scientific Paradigm (NSP) for the Twenty-First Century Physics Paradigm – based on the clear direct empirical validations of two of its unique "Critical Predictions"!*** (Significantly, this "G-D's Physics" NSP was shown to include both GRT & QM as mere "special cases" within the broader, more exhaustive theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" newly discovered above mentioned Universal Computational Formula, UCF, as outlined above).

Based on the abovementioned results validating "G-D's Physics" unique

"Critical Predictions" – as more accurate than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) Paradigm, "G-D's Physics" must be accepted (unequivocally) as the New Physics Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century!

We stand at a truly "historic time" – with this direct validation of "G-D's Physics" two unique Critical Predictions! Akin only to Eddington's direct empirical validation of one unique Critical Prediction of Einstein's General Relativity Theory (GRT) during the 1919 Solar Eclipse (e.g., empirically validating Einstein's prediction regarding Mercury's "double-valued" perihelion pathway curvature around the Sun – twice the value predicted by Newton's Classical Mechanics!) This "historic-turning point" or "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "Newtonian Classical Mechanics" (of Nineteenth Century Physics) to Einstein's GRT's New Scientific Paradigm (NSP) of Twentieth Century Physics – is therefore precisely equivalent to the current (pivotal) "historic turning-point" or (fundamental) "Paradigmatic Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal Random" Paradigm of 21st Century's GRT & QM – to the New (empirically validated based on these two unique Critical Predictions) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm!

Except that in the current basic Paradigmatic Shift from the Old MCR Paradigm to the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm we obtain a completely new understanding of the true nature, origin, dynamics and even "Ultimate Geulah Perfected State" of the universe – which completely "metamorphosizes" our basic conception of the entire physical universe: not as an "objective", "continuous", "independent", "stable", and "continuous" "physical" or "material" entity (and existence), but rather as merely representing a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of the singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality": which exists both "during" its continuous (extremely rapid: $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{sec}^{-1}$) computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s, and also solely exists (e.g., without the presence of any physical universe) "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s! Moreover, not only does the universe cease to exist as an "objective continuous, physical reality" – instead being viewed as merely a "transient-phenomenal manifestation" of this singular higher-ordered UCR, but it also revolutionizes out basic understanding of the entire (continuous) "origination", "sustenance", "development" and "steering" of the whole physical universe towards its "pre-planned" "Geulah-Perfected State", in which Science and Humanity recognizes this singularity of the UCR, alongside its "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" (which therefore also characterized Humanity's behavior and existence) – with the discovery and empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" as the New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm!

A Few (quite profound) theoretical ramifications ensue from this (unequivocal) acceptance of "G-D's Physics" as the New 21st Century Physics Paradigm:

A. Complete Unification of the Four Basic Physical Features!

First, it should be noted that based on the discovery of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels' Four basic Physical Features (e.g., of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{sec}^{-1}$ "G-D's Physics" has achieved (for the first time in Physics!) a complete unification of these Four Physical Features, i.e., within a singular "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF)! Indeed, the discovery of this singular higher-ordered UCP which simultaneously computes all Four Physical Features pointed at a unique capacity not only to unify between GRT & QM, but also to resolve the key "Gravitational Enigma" (as shown above)!

B. Principle Negation of the Old MCR's Paradigm's SRCS Computational Systems: The "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP)!

Specifically in the case of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's (implicit-

ly) assumed "Self-Referential Computational System" SRCS: it is assumed that it is only based on the direct physical interaction between certain (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter/Dark-Energy" (DMDE) elements and their direct (or even indirect) physical interactions with all (possible) "exhaustive components of the Universe" (Uec) of this SRCS System – that this SRCS System is able to compute whether these "exhaustive components of the Universe" (Uec) would remain the "same" or "different" (e.g., "Not Uec")?! Formally presented, this SRCS System of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm:

SRCS: {DMDE, Uec-aer } → "Uec-aer" or "Not Uec-aer"
 But, according to "G-d's Physics" "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) such a SRCS System inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational-indeterminacy" in the case of a "Negative" SRCS outcome, i.e., "SRCNS" – in which this SRCS System yields a "negative outcome":
 SRCNS: {DMDE, Uec-aer } → "Not Uec-aer"

In which it is assumed that this direct (or indirect) physical interaction between (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter"/"Dark-Energy" (DMDE) concepts and the "exhaustive components of the Universe- accelerated rate of expansion" (Uec) "cause" a "change" in this Uec-aer ("Not Uec-aer"); then this leads to an inevitable "logical-inconsistency" – since this SRCNS System states that the universe possesses both the initial Uec-aer rate of expansion and also possesses a "Not Uec-aer" (increased) rate of expansion! Obviously, such SRCNS "logical-inconsistency" inevitably also leads to an intrinsic state of "computational-indeterminacy" because such a "material-causal" SRCS/SRNC System cannot determine whether its initial Uec-aer or subsequent Not Uec-aer state of the universe's acceleration rate exists?! But, to the extent that we can validate "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion Rate" (UNCAER) – then this would negate the SRNC assumed computational structure of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm! Hence, the proposed "Critical-Prediction" of "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm that could differentiate it from the corresponding Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, e.g., regarding the "Big-Bang" Model and associated "Dark-Energy"/"Dark-Matter" should test for "G-d's Physics" predicted "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion Rate" (UNCAER), which coupled with the above CDP would unequivocally validate "G-d's Physics" New ACC Paradigm's conception of the UCP's singular higher-ordered continuous (simultaneous) computation- "dissolution"- re-computation- and evolution of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s). The results are taken from a series of scientific studies indicating the existence of a significant "gap" between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion (Scolnic et al. 2014; Riess et al. 2018a, 2019; Shajib et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2020)! As asserted by the abovementioned "G-d's Physics" Computational Duality Principle (CDP), This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) indicates a SRNC computational result yielded by the Old "Material-Causal" "Self-Referential Computational Structure" (SRCS):
 SRCNS: {DM/DE, Uec-er} ti → {"Not Uec-er"} ti+n

wherein it is assumed that it is the direct (or indirect) physical interaction between (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter"/"Dark-Energy" (DM/DE) concepts and the "exhaustive components of the Universe- expansion rate" (Uec-ar) that "causes" the universe to increase its acceleration rate with time?! But, as the CDP teaches us, such a SRNC computational state inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency", e.g., an apparent contradiction between the universe's stated expansion rate at_{ti} : as Uec-er; as opposed to its expansion rate as: Not Uec-er at $ti+n$?! This "logical-inconsistency" also invariably leads to an associated "computational-indeterminacy" – simply because such assumed SRCS(SRNC) computational

System is unable to decide whether the universe's accelerated rate should be "Uec-er" (at ti) or "Not Uec-er" (at $ti+n$)?! But, since according to the CDP we obtain clear empirical results (stated above) wherein the universe in fact exhibits an increase in its acceleration rate over time, e.g., as indicated by the "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG), therefore the CDP asserts that the basic SRCS/SRNC Computational System assumed by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (of RT & QM) must be negated and rejected! Instead, "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's CDP points at the existence of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/ Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec⁻¹"), thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every consecutive "minimal time-point"! Indeed, the empirically observed "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) conforms with "G-d's Physics" "Critical Prediction" of the "Universe's Non-Continuous Expansion Accelerated Rate" (UNCEAR) – which is further specified to occur during such (special) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" time-intervals as the "Jewish Rosh-Hashana" (JRH)! 3. The "Computational Duality Principle's" (CDP) Negation of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm : As mentioned above, one of the significant theoretical postulates of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm is called: the "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) which asserts that it is not possible, in principle, to compute any direct (or even indirect) relativistic or quantum physical relationship/s between any given "x" and "y" elements – from within their direct "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) assumed computational structure, but only from the higher-ordered singular "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP); This is because "G-d's Physics" "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) reveals that this "problematic" "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) computational structure characterizing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational-indeterminacy" that are intrinsic to this SRCS computational structure; But, since in all of those Relativistic or Quantum Systems, there exists robust empirical evidence that those Systems are capable of computing the outputted result of the System, therefore the CDP asserts that there must exist a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" computing the various states and existence of these Relativistic or Quantum Systems! The most general representation of this CDP can be given as: Whenever there exists a SRCS System (of the computational structure) assuming that the whole computation is determined solely at the same "di1" computational level:

SRCS {x, y} → "y" or "Not y"/di1
 Then this also raises the possibility of SRNC (e.g., "negative" "Not y" output):
 SRNC {x, y} → "Not y"/di1

which inevitably leads to "logical-inconsistency", since the "y" element seems to both "exist" and "not exist" at the same "di1" computational level?! SRNC {x, y} → "Not y"/di1 Such apparent "logical-inconsistency" also inevitably leads to an ensuing "computational indeterminacy", i.e., an apparent inability of such SRCS/SRNC to determine whether the "y" element exists or "doesn't exist", e.g., denoting a different altered value for this "y" element?! But, since there exists specific empirical evidence for any of these Relativistic or Quantum Systems' capability to determine and output a particular "y" value, therefore this contradicts the Duality Principle's above proof that such an assumed SRCS/ SRNC Computational System inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational indeterminacy" – therefore the CDP points at the existence of a singular higher-ordered UCP which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (as postulated by "G-d's Physics" "Universal Computational Principle", e.g., thereby producing the extremely rapid series of "Universal-Frames", UF's at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec⁻¹" comprising the entire physical universe at every such "minimal time-

point); Hence, below is a detailing of the various examples and manifestations of this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumed SRCS (& SRNCS) Computational Systems – which are all constrained and in fact negated by "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm, all pointing at the "Computational Duality Principle's" (CDP) asserted singular higher-ordered UCP (of "G-d's Physics New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm)!

A) The "Big-Bang Model":

More generally, the "Big-Bang" Model represents this Old "Material-Causal-Random" (MCR) Paradigm's assumption wherein it is the direct physical interaction/s between a certain "Nuclear Event" (NE) and a given "exhaustive components of the Universe" exhibiting a certain "expansion state" at (U-ec/es) that "causes" the universe's expansion state to "increase", e.g., that is, be "different" than the initial "expansion state", which can be represented as:

$$SRNCS \{NE, (U-ec/es)\} \rightarrow NOT (U-ec/es) /di1$$

Noteworthy is highlighting the implicit "material-causal" assumption of this "Big-Bang" Model's SRCS/SRNCS Computational System, e.g., whereby this SRCS/SRNCS Computational System assumes that it is solely based on this direct physical interaction between the NE and the initial state of the universe's expansion (U-ec/es) that this SRCS/SRNCS System is able to compute the different NOT (U-ec/es) state of the universe; Specifically that the entire SRCS/SRNCS computation exists at the same "di1" computational level of the SRCS! But, such a SRCS/SRNCS Computational System inevitably leads to a "logical-inconsistency":

$$SRNCS \{NE, (U-ec/es)\} \rightarrow NOT (U-ec/es)/di1!$$

This implies that the SRCS/SRNCS Computational System assumed by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm inevitably also leads to an apparent "computational indeterminacy", e.g., an apparent inability of this SRCS/SRNCS Computational System to determine whether the universe will remain its initial (U-ec/e)s state or evolve into the latter "NOT (U-ec/es)"! But, since there exists robust empirical evidence indicating the existence of a significant "gap" between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion (Scolnic et al. 2014; Riess et al. 2018a, 2019; Shajib et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2020) indicates that there exists a Computational System that is capable of determining the universe's accelerated rate of expansion – which actually increases "non-continuously" with time: "NOT (U-ec/es)"! Hence, according to the CDP, this Computational System cannot comprise the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's – but only the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational System" (UCP), which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., at the incredible rate of "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec' of a series of "Universal Frames")!

B) General Relativity Theory (GRT) "Einstein's Equations":

Another (key) manifestation of this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's basic assumption is GRT's Einstein's Equations basic "material-causal" assumption: According to Einstein's Equations, the presence of certain "Massive Objects" (MO) and their direct physical interaction with "Space-Time" "causes" a change in the curvature level of this "Space-Time":

$$SRNCS \{MO, STc\} \rightarrow "NOT STc"/di1$$

But, once again, such a SRNCS output of the SRCS Computational System basic computational structure inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency", i.e., in intrinsic inability of the SRCS (or SRNCS) assumed Computational System to determine whether the initial STc or the subsequent "NOT STc" state of "Space-Time" should exist – since they're both intrinsic

elements within the same SRCS/SRNCS "di1" computational level!
 SRNCS {MO, STc} → "NOT STc"/di1

Therefore, once again the CDP points at the ensuing "computational-indeterminacy" of such a SRNCS Computational System, which cannot decide whether the resulting state of Relativistic System should remain at the initial STc state or undergo an additional curvature of Space-Time as in the more "curved Space-Time" state, e.g., signified by "NOT STc"?! But, since the abovementioned clear empirical indication of the existence of a significant "gap" between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion (Scolnic et al. 2014; Riess et al. 2018a, 2019; Shajib et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2020) represents a "special-case" of GRT's Einstein's Equations, then this indicates that the Computational System that is capable of determining the universe's accelerated rate of expansion (associated with Einstein's abovementioned SRCS/SRNCS assumed Computational System); Therefore, once again, the CDP points at the existence of a singular higher-ordered UCP which simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel's four basic physical features -of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", giving rise to an extremely rapid series of UF's frames; Indeed, "G-d's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" (ACC) Paradigm was shown to offer an alternative computational account for the apparent "material-causal" "curvature of Space-Time by massive objects" – i.e., based on "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) novel computational definitions of the four basic physical features by this singular higher-ordered UCP, and the new "Universal Computational Formula" which completely unifies (for the first time in Physics) between these four basic physical features of the universe:

$$S: (f_i\{x,y,z\}[UF(i)] + \dots f_j\{x,y,z\}[UF(n)]) / h * n \{UF's\} \text{ such that: } f_j\{x,y,z\}[UF(n) \leq f_i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\} [UF's(i\dots n)]$$

where the "space" measure of a given object (or event) is computed based on a "Frame-consistent" computation that adds the specific UF's (x,y,z) localization across a series of UF's [i...n] which nevertheless do not exceed the threshold of Planck's constant per each number ("n") of frames (e.g., thereby providing "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's computational definition of "space" as "Frame-consistent" UF's measure! Conversely, the "energy" of any given "object" (e.g., whether it is the spatial dimensions of an object or event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on the event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on "Frame-inconsistent" differences of a given "object's" location or size across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light ("c") multiplied by the number of UF's across which the "object's" energy value is computed by the

$$UCP: E: (f_i\{x,y,z\}[UF(i)] - \dots f_j\{x,y,z\}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\} \text{ such that: } f_j\{x,y,z\}[UF(n) > f_i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\} [UF's(i\dots n)]$$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's. In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes): $M: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i\dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$ where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical): such that:

$$M: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i...n)] \leq n * h [UF's(i...n)]$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value. In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

$$T: \Sigma[O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] \neq O(i...n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i...n)\} / c * n\{UF's(i...n)\} \text{ such that: } T: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i...n)] \leq c * h [UF's(i...n)]$$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light. Universal Computational Formula (UCF):

C) Challenging Quantum Mechanics' MCR Assumed "Probability-Wave Function" Collapse:

Another important manifestation of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's basic assumption which is challenged and negated by "G-d's Physics" New "Computational Duality Principle" is Quantum Mechanics' "material-causal" assumption wherein it is the direct physical interaction between a given subatomic "probe" (P) element and a corresponding subatomic ("un-collapsed") "target's probability wave-function" (Tu-wf) – which is assumed to "cause" the "collapse of the probability wave-function" into a single "complimentary" (space/energy or time/mass) value:

$$SRNCS: \{P, Tu-wf\} \rightarrow \text{"NOT Tu-wf"}/di1.$$

But, as stated above, according to the CDP such a SRNCS Computational System inevitably leads to "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational-indeterminacy":

$$SRNCS: \{P, Tu-wf\} \rightarrow \text{"NOT Tu-wf"}/di1$$

Wherein this assumed SRNCS Computational System cannot decide whether the target element should exhibit its assumed "un-collapsed" probability wave function values or the single "complimentary" (space/energy or mass/time) "collapsed" value?! However, since we know empirically that any such QM System is capable of determining the "collapsed" single complimentary value of any given subatomic target element – therefore the CDP points at the existence of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe as an extremely rapid series of Universal Frames (UF's) at the incredible rate of "c² /h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec! As outlined and delineated extensively (previously) the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm expands, embeds and transcends the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's conception of QM's "single spatial-temporal" "particle", "multiple spatial-temporal" "wave" – and "exhaustive" "Universal Frames" (UF's) computational perspectives which are all embedded within the UCP's singular higher-ordered (integrated) "Universal Computational Formula" (outlined above). 4. Discussion: Theoretical Ramifications of "G-d's Physics" CDP Negation of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm Hence, we see that underlying the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm is a fundamental "material-causal" "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) which inevitably leads to a both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational-indeterminacy" which are negated by empirical evidence indicating that those Relativistic and Quantum Systems are capable of determining their specific outcomes – which according to the CDP points at the existence of singular higher-ordered UCP that computes

simultaneously all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s (e.g., at the incredible rate of "c² /h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec!) Once again, "G-d's Physics" New 21st century "A-Causal Computation" (ACC) Paradigm's "Computational Duality Principle's" (CDP) negation of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's fundamental "material-causal" assumption – not only negates some of the most basic assumptions associated with the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (abovementioned), including: a) The "Big-Bang" Model's assumed origination and assumed creation of all "mass", "energy", "space" and "time" by an initial "nuclear event" which is assumed to "cause" the accelerated expansion of the universe; b) The existence of purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" (DM/ DE) concepts which are assumed to "cause" the accelerated expansion of the physical universe; c) General Relativity Theory's Einstein's Equations' basic assumed evolution of the universe by certain "Massive-Objects" (MO) which are assumed to "cause" the "curvature of Space-Time" (and converse determination of those "massive-objects" travelling-pathways as "caused" or determined by this curvature of Space-Time); d) QM's assumed "material-causal" "collapse" of the subatomic target's "probability wave-function" as "caused" by its direct physical interaction with a corresponding subatomic "probe" element into a singular complimentary "space-energy" or "mass-time" value; The negation of each of these manifestations of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm basic "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) computational structure was proven (above) based on the "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) which indicated that such basic SRCS/SRNCS Computational Systems inevitably lead to both "logical-inconsistency" and associated "computational-indeterminacy" that are negated by clear empirical evidence indicating the capacity of these Relativistic or Quantum Systems to determine their respective computational outcomes; hence, the CDP pointed at the necessary existence of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe, e.g., for each consecutive UF's frame/s! But, even beyond this (highly significant) negation of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying GRT and QM basic conception of the origination, sustenance and dynamics of the physical universe; the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm was shown to completely integrate both Relativistic and Quantum Models within the singular higher-ordered UCP's "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF): Universal Computational Formula (UCF): In fact, once we realize based on "G-d's Physics" additional (profound) theoretical postulates of the "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR), which essentially point at the sole and singular reality of this "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" or "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) – which exists uniformly, continuously and constantly both "during" its computation of each consecutive UF's frame/s (e.g., simultaneously computing every exhaustive spatial pixel's four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time"), and also exists solely without the presence of any physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s; as opposed to the only "transient" and "phenomenal" existence of all of the universe's exhaustive spatial pixels – existing only "during" the UCP's computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s but not "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frames; therefore according to these two "Computational Invariance Principle" and "Universal Consciousness Reality" theoretical postulates there only exists only singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR or UCP) which exists continuously, constantly and uniformly both "during" its manifestation as the physical universe (through its sole computation of each consecutive UF's frame/s) and "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s in which only this singular UCR exists (without the presence of any physical universe); Viewed from this singular higher-ordered "G-d's Physics" "UCR" perspective, the entire universe is seen (and realized) as representing a manifestation of this singular UCR which exists uniformly and constantly. Finally, as shown previously, due to "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's realization that there truly only exists one singular higher-ordered UCR Reality, and based on the (previously delineated) UCP's/UCR's "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions"

characterizing this singular UCR Reality, we reach a profound new conceptualization and appreciation of the true (singular) UCR Reality underlying- creating- "dissolving" (e.g., "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frames!) and evolving every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the whole universe); Indeed, according to the abovementioned (and previously delineated) "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions – Universal Computational Formula" (THCD-UCF) this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR is characterized by such "Divine" properties as "All-Goodness", the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle", "Oneness", "Peace" and "Harmony" and aims to evolve the whole physical universe towards its "Ultimate Geulah Goal" Moral, Spiritual and Physical State of Perfection, in which the whole of Humanity and Science will recognize this singular UCR "Divine Reality"...

D) The UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (THCD's)

"G-D's Physics" New (empirically proven) Scientific Paradigm discovered the existence of the UCP's "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (THCD's):

1) The UCR's "Wisdom/Free-Will" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חכמה")

The UCP's first (initial highest) Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the UCP's "Wisdom/Free-Will" which relates to the UCP's complete "Free-Will" in its computation and "laws" pertaining to the successive computation- "dissolution" re-computation- and evolution- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (e.g., since it is not bound by any "material-causal" physical interactions and it possesses Infinite Wisdom); Indeed, this initial UCR's "Free-Will/Wisdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension is characterized by a "Free-Will/Wisdom" of the UCR's initial conception of the creation of an apparently "separate" and "independent" physical universe – which seems to exist "independently" of the UCR's sole creation, sustenance and evolution of it(!?), but which will nevertheless evolve into the ultimate "Goal" of creating Human-Beings possessing the most "expansive" form of Consciousness that will recognize and appreciate the sole existence and "All-Goodwill" characteristics of this singular higher-ordered UCR! It represents the UCP's initial impetus and Wisdom's conception of the possibility of creating an apparently "independent" physical universe (e.g., from its true sole "Universal Consciousness Reality's" sustenance of it) that will "evolve" the most "expansive" form of Human Consciousness leading to a recognition and appreciation of the singularity of this UCR's "Infinite Wisdom", "All-Goodness" characteristics!

2) The UCP's "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension ("בינה"):

The UCP's secondary Hierarchical Computational Dimension of "All-Goodness/Computation" (בינה) regards the further development of the UCR's "Hierarchical Computational Plan" execution of this initial "Free-Will/Wisdom" general conception of the creation of an apparently "independent" physical universe that evolves into Humanity's ultimate "Geulah" State of recognizing, appreciating and living in accordance with this singular UCR's "All-Goodness" characteristics: This secondary "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension conceives of the UCP's principle computation of each and every exhaustive spatial pixel – possessing the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time", which allows for the creation of apparently "independent" "living-organisms", e.g., each possessing varying degrees of "awareness" or "Consciousness", and existing apparently "independent" of their true-sole- source of the Universal Consciousness Reality!?! Indeed, it is this apparent "independence" of every Biological form (e.g., plants, animals and human-beings) from the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which manifests the UCR's "All-Goodness" benevolent characteristic, since it sustains all of Life – continuously creating- "dissolving"- re-creating- and evolving every living form throughout its life-cycle, as well as produces ever more "expansive" form of Consciousness (e.g., leading up to human-beings, as further delineated in the third Hierarchical Computa-

tional Dimension, below):

3) The UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/דעת).

The UCR's fourth Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the "Reversed-Time 'Geulah' Goal" which describes (for the first time in the UCR's successive hierarchical manifestation of the physical universe) the UCR's full-complete "Blueprint Architectural Hierarchical Plan" for creating and "evolving" the entire physical universe in order to create- progressively more "expansive" forms of Consciousness, i.e., from "inanimate", "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal" of Humanity's (and Science's) recognition of the sole and singular reality of the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR); It describes the UCR's entire Hierarchical Computational Plan for evolving and manifesting increasingly more "expansive" forms of this singular UCR – e.g., from inanimate "matter", through "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the most "expansive" form of "Collective Human Consciousness" recognizing and leading a "Perfected: Moral, Spiritual & Physical State": in which Humanity recognizes the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) including the basic, "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which compels human-beings and Humanity as a whole to lead a Moral, Harmonious & Peaceful Human Existence. It is termed "Daat" (דעת) in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah tradition because it signifies the UCR's "Knowledge" or "Plan" for the entire evolution of the physical universe – leading to the UCR's "Ultimate Geulah Goal"! Indeed, this fourth Hierarchical Computational "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension offers a new profound insight into the UCR's overall "pre-planned successive evolution" of the entire physical universe – "conceived" of and "pre-planned" from the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" in a "reversed direction" through all "past"- "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" (based on every Individual Human Consciousness' Moral Choice/s made at each point in time, as will be described in the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension)! Just as an Architect constructing a complex and elaborate building will pre-plan all of the details of this complex and beautiful building in an Architectural "Blue-Print", e.g., including all of the details regarding the necessary "construction-steps" to attain the desired "end-goal" of the full Elaborate Complex Building, so it is suggested the UCR also "pre-planned" all of the necessary "past", "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" of all the Universal Frames depicting the evolution of the entire physical universe in order to evolve the progressive ("inanimate" and "animate": plants, animals and human-beings) forms of Consciousness leading to the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" of Humanity (and Science)! Hence, the fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/דעת) signifies the UCR's complete "Knowledge" or "Plan" for evolving the entire physical universe – from inanimate matter through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards the Perfected "Geulah Goal State", and it is computed and "corrected" to reach this Perfected "Geulah -State" through a continuous "adjustment" process of the UCR based on its later "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" and closely associated "UCR's Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" (as listed below).

4) The fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חסד"/Chessed):

This "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" relates to the actual execution of the UCR's fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah -Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, i.e., based on a Compassionate ("Chessed/חסד") Moral Principle which allows every human-being to "correct" any of his or her "Immoral Action/s" through the UCR's computation of an equivalent "future" corresponding to any such "immoral action", which would allow that "offending human-being" to experience the same kind (and degree) of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon another Individual Human-Being, so that the "offending" person could make a sincere "Teshuva" (termed so in the Jewish Tradition) signifying a sincere remorse

and accompanying conscious choice not to repeat any such "immoral-action/s" in the future! Since we've seen that the whole Goal of the UCR's evolution of the entire physical universe is solely towards reaching that "Perfected Geulah State" in which all human-beings (and Humanity more generally) would recognize the Oneness, Morality and Peace characterizing the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) and lead a Moral, Peaceful and Harmonious life, therefore the means for reaching this end Goal of "Geulah " may be attained through the (fourth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Dimension – which produces a "moral correction-mechanism" allowing every individual human-being (and Humanity as a whole) to "perfect" its moral behavior and awareness this through this "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle"! A "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized which tries to demonstrate the "correction-dynamics" of this UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium mechanism: A scenario in which a Trampoline Sheath is placed with a "Metal-Bar" connecting two particular "points" on its surface, such that when one of these particular "point" "decides" to "inflict-pain/suffering" upon the other "point" by pressing the "Metal-Bar" against that other point, we realize that "automatically" the "suffering point" will "push-back" the same "Metal-Bar" against the initially "aggressive-point" to "balance" the Trampoline-Sheath back to its original "resting state"... This "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized to explain the "UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which constantly and continuously strives to restore the "Oneness", "Peace" and "Harmony" characterizing the UCR's basic nature, e.g., to "correct" for any "moral-imbalance" created by any single one Individual Human Consciousness (person) deciding any "immoral-choice" against another given individual which brings about a "balancing-act" of the UCR creating an equivalent situation in which that "inflicting-pain/suffering" individual would have to experience him/herself the same degree and kind of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon the other individual, in order to realize the "inseparability" and "Oneness" of the UCR underlying both Human Consciousness...

5) The Fifth UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Devorah"/"גבורה"):

Denotes the UCR's actual translation of the fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" into a computation of all "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each Individual human-being for every moral choice that he/she makes at any given point in time! In other words, the UCR simultaneously computes for all human-beings in the world one of multiple possible "future/s" based on each of these individual human-beings' "moral/immoral choice/s", geared towards executing the above mentioned "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" on order to "teach" or "correct" each individual human-being's moral choice/s and realization of the underlying singular "Oneness" of the UCR comprising all individual human beings and more generally the entire physical universe (including all of its "inanimate" and "animate" forms); This steers Humanity and the entire world towards the realization of the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State aimed for by the singular higher-ordered UCR reality!

6) The UCR's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("תפארת"/"Tiferet"):

The sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" Hierarchical Computational Dimension postulates that the actual manifestation of the entire physical universe critically depends upon the UCR's close relationship with a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" aimed towards that UCR! In other words, according to "G-d's Physics" New 21st century Paradigm, the UCR's actual computation of all past- present and "multiple possible future/s" Universal Frames (UF's) constituting each consecutive Year's (time-frame) critically depends upon the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus", in which Millions of individual human-beings simultaneously focus on this singular higher-ordered UCR during a "special time-interval", i.e., such as at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" New Year two-days' time-interval in which Millions of Jews focus collectively

upon this singular higher-ordered UCR! This sixth Hierarchical Computational "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" instigates the UCR's computation of an entire New Year derived from the (fifth) UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" – allowing for the entire physical universe development for an entire New Year, based on the already determined "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human -being for the entire New Year! One of the direct empirical ramifications of this sixth "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Computational Dimension" correlated with one of the (two) unique "Critical-Predictions" differentiating the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of both Relativity Theory and Quantum Mechanics, i.e., relating to "G-d's Physics" prediction that during the "special-time" of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" taking place every Jewish New-Year's "Rosh-Hashana" two days interval (e.g., this year occurring at : Sep. 7th & 8th , 2021) there will be a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion" of the entire physical universe! This is due to "Collective Human Consciousness Focus (sixth) Hierarchical Computational Dimension's assertion wherein such a 'Collective Human Consciousness Focus', wherein Millions of Jews (all around the world) collectively focus on- and pray towards- this singular higher-ordered UCR, which is assumed to bring about the UCR's computation of all of the "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" UF's for all individual human beings – as well as the accelerated new expansion rate for the entire physical universe for the subsequent New Jewish Year! Alongside the previous (third) "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" realization that the UCR "pre-plans" the entire evolution of the universe including its evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings all leading towards the Ultimate "Geulah Goal" of Human Moral and Spiritual Perfection and recognition of the singularity and "All-Goodness" nature of this UCR, we can understand that the UCR opts to compute an entire "New (Jewish) Year" in response to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Dimension – which manifests also in the "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe" during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special "Collective Human Consciousness Focus"! Obviously, as will be elaborated below, to the extent that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm will be validated empirically, then this will lead to the acceptance of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm as the New Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics, since it negates the existence of "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" and significantly differs from the corresponding predictions of both RT & QM, representing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of 20th century Physics! The Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol given to this sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Hierarchical Computational Dimension" is "תפארת/Tiferet" which translates as "Glorification" because it signifies such "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Glorification- or focus on- and prayer towards- this singular, higher-ordered UCR.

7) The Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("ניצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal"):

Signifies the UCR's actual simultaneous computation of all of the two "Object – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) values for all objects comprising the entire physical universe for each single UF frame, based on all of the previous (above mentioned) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions; it represents the beginning of the actual manifestation of any single UF's frame portrayal of the entire physical universe, which fulfills and advances the UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension, and furthers the "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus" computation of an entire New Year's ("past", "present" and "multiple future/s") UF's frames – now being executed for each single UF's frame's constitution of all comprising object's (mass and time) values! It is also represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol of "ניצח/Eternal" or "Victory" because the UCR's actual computation of any single UF frame's comprising Object's (mass and time) values all constituting objects indeed signifies the advancement of the UCR's "Reversed Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical

Computational Dimension", which represents the "Eternal" or Ultimate "Geulah -State" of the world.

8) The "Teshuva" (תשובה) / "הוד" / "Hod" / "Forgiveness" Eighth Hierarchical Computational Dimension:

Signifies the UCR's allowance for a "Teshuva" / "repentance" of every individual human-being prior to the actual execution of the seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("ניח" / "Netzach" / "Eternal" – wherein if any individual person choses to ask "forgiveness" from the other person upon which it inflicted pain or suffering as well as from the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR) and makes a conscious resolute decision to not repeat any such wrongdoing moral action/s (which constitutes the Jewish term of "Teshuva"); in such case, the UCR's Eighth "Teshuva" Hierarchical Computational Dimension will re-compute and in fact alter the already selected Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("ניח" / "Netzach" / "Eternal") values computed for that individual human-being's computed immediate pending "future" UF, i.e., replacing the "correcting" equivalent UF frame in which this "offending" individual would have to experience an "equivalent" painful experience (to the one experienced by the person offended by the "immoral choice" made by him/her) with a "positive" immediate future UF frame – based on the fact that that individual human-being already made "Teshuva" (sincere repentance and resolute decision not to repeat any such "immoral" action/s!) It is represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "הוד" / "Hod" which can be translated as "Magnanimity" because it portrays the UCR's magnanimous "forgiveness" capacity to allow for any individual human-being to make a sincere "Teshuva", thereby altering the whole evolution of the universe, based on the "corrected" moral choices of all of its individual human-beings; Indeed, it is a magnanimous UCR that allows for Humanity's "partnership" and "active role" in advancing its Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State, at every point in time...

9) The Ninth UCR's "Actual Computed Object Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("יסוד" / "Yesod" (Foundation)):

Signifies the UCR's actually computed values for all of the objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s which is based on all previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions! It is therefore represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabballah term of "יסוד" / "Yessod" or "Foundation" the UCR's actual computed Object (mass/time) values of all constituting objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame! Note, however, that this "יסוד" / "Foundation" Ninth Hierarchical Computational Dimension does not (yet) contain the two other essential UCP's "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features which are necessary to execute and actual UF's frame of the universe at any minimal time-point, which is computed by the Tenth Hierarchical Computational Dimension; This also correlates to the fact that the UCR's integral and essential (forth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle's" Hierarchical

Computational Dimension's "moral-balancing" characteristic of the UCR's continuous and constant advancement of the universe (and Humanity) towards the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" Perfected Moral and Spiritual State necessarily involves the UCR's computation of "pairs" of "offending-offended" individual human-beings, which would have to experience the equivalent "corrected" Moral State, e.g., involving their "placement" within the same UF's frame/s (once again, computed by the UCR's Tenth "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula" / "מלכות" / "Kingdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below:)

10) The "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula" / "מלכות" / "Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר" / "Keter-Infinitude" ("Crown")):

This tenth concluding Hierarchical Computational Dimension signifies the UCR's actual computation of each consecutive Universal Frame (UF), including all of its four basic physical features of "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time), and "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire universe (for each minimal time-point UF's frame/s)! It consumes all of the previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions as comprising any single consecutive UF's frame/s, thereby executing and "building" the "Kingdom" of the UCR's series of UF's inevitably leading to Its "Ultimate Geulah -Goal" Perfected State of the world and the universe! This includes the full integration of the previous (ninth) "יסוד" / "Yessod" – "Foundation" Hierarchical Computational Dimension' comprising only the two "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) physical features associated with every exhaustive object comprising the entire physical universe, together with the two other "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features that are necessary in order to create any single (consecutive) UF's frame! It also necessitates the direct involvement and "power" of the Infinite UCR's Essence (or "כתר" / "Crown") as it is called in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabballah Tradition which (as it were) "stands alone" in its infinitude – beyond the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", i.e., Prior to its manifesting of the entire physical universe through its associated "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions"! Indeed, as can be glanced from this "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" (below), the direct "involvement" of this "כתר" / "Keter" – Infinitude ("Crown") Essence of the UCR is seen both "prior to" and "above" the UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions ("standing alone" as the "כתר" / "Keter" - Crown" of these Ten Dimensions) and is also apparent in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" – in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula" / "מלכות" / "Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר" / "Keter-Infinitude" ("Crown")); This is because in order to manifest, integrate and compute the entire physical universe simultaneously – at the incredible rate of "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ (sec) for each exhaustive spatial pixel it necessitates the Infinite Wisdom and Essence of the UCR!

Figure 4: THE TEN HIERARCHICAL DIMENSIONS' UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA (THD-UCF):

E) "G-D's Physics" New "Gimatria", "Dynamic-Moral Principle" & "Geulah Driven" Universe!

We now reach the "culmination" of our new understanding of the physical universe, which is based on the entire corpus of over 100 scientific (peer-reviewed) articles dedicated to the discovery, delineation and empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics! We've already seen that the entire physical universe does not exist "continuously" or "independently" of its continuous "computation" - "dissolution" - "re-computation" and "development" by the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" or "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR); and in fact, that the entire physical universe may be viewed (or regarded) merely as a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR), which exists only "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s (as solely computed by this singular UCR: simultaneously for all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s), but "ceases" to exist, and "dissolves" back into the singularity or the UCP/UCR "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s!

As also described in previous articles (Bentovish, see detailed References) the UCP's extremely rapid computation of the series of Universal Frames (and of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising it) is primarily based upon a few characteristics associated with the UCP's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions and associated Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula (THCD's-UCF), including its delineation of the Gimatria's (alphabetic Hebrew numeric values associated with each letter comprising the Hebrew name of any given object or even person!) Generally speaking, we may describe the "extremely complex" and "infinitely intelligent" capacities of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (or UCR), there are "six layers" (or phases) of this singular UCP/UCR:

1) The UCP's Three Key Initial (TKI) HCD's: "General Blueprint Universal Plan" (GCC, CMD, DEMP, GDD)

The Three Key Initial (TKI) HCD's comprise the "General Blueprint Plan" for the UCP outlines the continuous "origination" - "sustenance" and "development" of the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of the universe, e.g., in which the singularity of the UCP will be recognized by Humanity (and Science) alongside its "sublime characteristics" of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" & "Harmony" which will therefore also characterize Humanity's existence and behavior! It therefore "contains" the key "Consistency Computational Principles" guiding the UCP's execution of the Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' operation, as well as all other ensuing computations carried out by the next five successive levels of the UCP (delineated below); Generally speaking, it contains these "Computational Principles":

2) Consciousness-Moral Development (CMD)

Relates to the UCP's "General Guiding Principle" of "steering" the whole universe from Its initial "inanimate" matter state through successive "animate": plants, animals, and human-beings – leading towards Humanity's Ultimate "Geulah Perfected Goal" state! (It should be mentioned that due to "G-D's Physics" Collective Human Consciousness Focus theoretical postulate and empirical validation of its unique UNCIARE "Critical Prediction" based on the abovementioned Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion (HubbleTension), therefore this CMD Guiding Principle is also associated with "G-D's Physics" "Six Days' Creation Model", SDCM, as outlined above)

3) The "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" (DEMP)

Another key "General Guiding Principle" is one of the THCD's called the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" (DEMP) which also characterizes

es one of the "sublime characteristics" of the UCP/UCR associated with its Moral nature! According to this DEMP, the UCP contains a "Multi-Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" which comprises all "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human-being based on his/her "Moral Choice/s" (at every point in time)! According to this UCP's DEMP ("Guiding Principle") whenever any individual human-being makes (for instance) any "immoral choice" ("G-d forbid") and inflicts "pain/suffering" upon another individual human-being, then this "triggers" the UCP's DEMP's "balancing moral computation" which computes an equivalent "negative situation" in which that individual human-being that "inflicted pain/suffering" upon another individual human-being would have to experience ("G-d forbid") an "equivalently negative situation" – that would most likely lead him/her to make "Teshuvah", (e.g., a Jewish term denoting a sincere sense of remorse and associated conscious decision not to repeat any such "immoral choice/s"! Indeed, as outlined above (and previously), to the extent that any such individual human-being makes such a sincere "Teshuvah" (also represented by the eighth HCD of "Teshuva" ("הרהר"), then this will "prevent" and (indeed) "omit" the UCP's ("need" to present) any subsequent "equivalent negative situation" UF's frame/s (for that individual human-being), because the whole "purpose" of the UCP's execution of the DEMP is to "balance", "correct" and "steer" each individual human-being towards a "morally-balanced" state of Humanity in which the whole of Humanity views and regards each other as "inseparable parts" of the same singular higher-ordered Moral "Universal Consciousness Reality"! (As noted previously, the same UCP's DEMP also "renumerates" each individual human-being by presenting an "equivalent-positive" situation for any "good moral choice/s" made by any individual human-being to assist another individual human-being as well!).

4) Geulah Directed Development (GDD)!

Perhaps the most important (key) "Guiding Principle" is the UCP's "Geulah-Directed Development" (GDD) of the whole physical universe – whose whole "pre-planning" by the singular higher-ordered UCP has been geared and directed to attain this "Ultimate-Geulah Goal Perfected State" of the universe! It therefore "overarches" and "leads" the other (abovementioned) two UCP's "Guiding Principles" – all aimed at fulfilling this UCP's (singular higher-ordered) "Ultimate Geulah Perfected Goal"! Therefore, we can see that this "germinal" "Geulah Perfected Goal" of the UCP (e.g., including its three abovementioned ensuing Consistency Computation elements of: CMD, DEMP & GDD).

5). The Seven Secondary Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (HCD's) "Geulah-Directed Universe"!

Based upon the TKI-HCCD's (three initial HCD's) "General Blueprint Plan" for the whole origination, sustenance and development of the universe then leads to the "secondary layer" of the "Seven Secondary HCD's" which are utilized by the UCP as its means for "executing" and "directing" the continuous development of the universe (e.g., and of every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising it!) – which are aimed at "steering" the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of Humanity & Science! As we can clearly see in the Diagram (and as outlined and delineated in previous articles), the Three Key Initial (TKI) HCD's provide us with a detailed "Geulah Directed Blueprint Plan for "steering" the universe towards this "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State" – based on the (first HCD of the UCP's) "Wisdom/Free Will" "desire" to create the world (and specifically our planet Earth – filled with the various forms of inanimate matter, and animate: plants, animals, all leading to the creation of human-beings endowed with a unique conscious "Moral-Choice!"); subsequently, the second HCD of "Computation" also contains the UCP's "Consistency" CMD "germinal" conception (e.g., comprising the conception of the universe's whole entire development from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings and leading up to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected" State! The next seven HCD's actually execute (and fulfill)

the UCP's DEMP & GDD "Guiding Principles" (as previously delineated): Succinctly stated, the fourth HCD of "Goodwill/DEMP" represents the UCP's enables each individual human-being (e.g., as well as the whole of Humanity) to "balance" and in fact "enhance" his/her "Moral Stance", i.e., assisting Humanity (and each individual human-being comprising it) to realize our "inseparability" from this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR, and therefore "stop" and (principally) "negate" any "negative-immoral" action and in fact enhance (and "encourage") all "moral-good behavior" towards our fellow human-beings! The fourth HCD of "Multi-Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" represents the actual execution of the UCP's "bank" of all "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" (e.g., contained within the whole corps of the "pre-planned course" of the universe's "Complete Journey" from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings – and all of the "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human-being necessary in order to bring Humanity towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe! The sixth HCD of the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (at the Jewish Rosh Hashanah: CHCF-JRH) represents the UCP's allocation of a single (whole) Jewish Year (segment) from the (previous "Multi-Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" spanning the whole "preplanned corpus" of the entire universe's development) containing all of the necessary "events" and "situations" found within a single "Jewish Year" that are "pre-planned" to "execute" and "balance" the DEMP in order to "uplift" Humanity "ever-closer" to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal State" (e.g., during this New Jewish Year)! The seventh HCD of the "UCP's Computed Potential Object" relates (according to "G-D's Physics" previously delineated novel computational definitions of any given "Object's") two associated physical features of "mass" (i.e., "Object-consistent") and "time" (i.e., "Object-inconsistent")! This seventh UCP's HCD computation takes into account all previous UCP's HCD's cumulating any given "Object's" (e.g., any individual human-being's according to his/her "moral-choice/s", or any other "animate" or "animate" "Object's" associated moral value/s and ensuing DEMP's based computed "Object" ("mass" and "time" values)! Subsequently, the UCP's eighth HCD of "Teshuvah" (as outlined above) allows for the possibility of any individual human-being's making a sincere "teshuva" (e.g., as explained above and previously) – which then "alters" (and even "prevents") the UCP's presentation of any potentially "negative situation/s" for any given individual human-being based on such a (sincere) "teshuva" (by that individual human-being)! The ninth HCD of the "UCP's Actual Computed Object Four Physical Features" represents the UCP's culmination of the actual computation for the next (subsequent) UF's frame's computation of the four basic physical features (e.g., of "mass", "energy", "space" and "energy") – based on all of the previous eight HCD's! Note that this ninth UCP's "Actual Computed Object" – even though it contains also the two (additional) "Frame" related physical features, e.g., "Frame-consistent" ("space") and "Frame-inconsistent" ("energy") – it still "lacks" the actual ability to "materialize" any given exhaustive spatial pixel or any object (based upon these extremely complex and intelligent computations)!? According to "G-D's Physics THCD's detailed analysis, this requires the "infinite intelligence and power" of the UCP- which Itself "executes" and "carries out" this "materialization" of all exhaustive spatial pixels and objects in the universe (comprising any consecutive UF's frame/s) in the Tenth HCD's "UCP's 'Infinite' Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Materialization"! Indeed, as we will see in the accumulation of all the five detailed "layers" (or phases) of the UCP's singular (extremely complex) computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (and objects) in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s) far exceeds even our most "wild imagination" regarding the "infinite": "complexity", "intelligence" and "power" required in order to accumulate and integrate these "disparate" ("infinitely complex") five (integrated) lawyer of the UCP's (simultaneous) computation for each exhaustive spatial pixel/s in the universe!

It is important to note that "encapsulated" within the Seven Secondary HCD's are also found the Geulah Directed Development (GDD) – found

within the "Good-Will" HCD; the entire "Conscious-Moral Development" (CMD) – found within the "Multi-Spatial-Temporal-Reservoir" (MSTR) containing the UCP's "reservoir" of all the UF's of the entire universe's "pre-planned history", i.e., corpus of all "past", "present" and "future" UF's frame/s, e.g., including its development from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings (and leading up to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe!)

6). Gimatria Based UCP's Computation of All Exhaustive Spatial Pixels' Objects!

Next, we have to add the UCP's (successive) computation of every exhaustive spatial object in the universe – in terms of the UCP's computation of its "physical characteristics" based on its Hebrew name's "Gimatria": i.e., alphabetic-numeric value/s comprised of each of its "five" (or less or more) letters which correspond to the (Seven Secondary HCD's) initial five HCD's: Good-Will (חסד), MSTR (גבורה), UNCIARE-JRH (תפארת), UCP's Potential Computed Object (חצנ), Teshuva (דוה)! According to "G-D's Physics" novel conception of the manner in which the UCP "originates" all exhaustive objects in the universe (previously delineated) the UCP extremely rapid computation of the series of UF's (comprising the entire physical universe at every "minimal time-point") at the incredible rate of " $c/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50}$ sec"! the UCP "allocates" "five zero's out of the 50 zero's (e.g., power of minus 50!) – the first 5 zeroes are allocated to the UCP's computation of the given object's first (Seven Secondary HCD's) of "Good-Will" which is associated that object's first letter (e.g., as it is computed relative to the other four remaining letters in that five-letter object's name; if there are less- or more- than those five "template" Gimatria Based UCP's computation, then there is a "compensation" or "addition" by the missing letters that are added to the "missing" letters or "last fifth letter"! Thus, for instance the Hebrew word for a human-being is "אדם" which only contains three letters: the Gimatria alphabetic value of the first letter "א" is "1" – which is assigned to the first (Secondary Seven) HCD of "Good-Will" ("חסד") which receives the highest value in terms of the "core characterization" of the "spiritual facet" underlying this object's subsequent Four Physical Features! If we were to give a metaphoric image to the manner in which these "Gimatria-based" alphabetic numeric vales are associated with groups of "five zero's" – for each of these five initial (Seven Secondary HCD's): Good-Will (חסד), MSTR (גבורה), UNCIARE-JRH (תפארת), UCP's Potential Computed Object (נצח), Teshuva (דוה) are subsequently translated into the Four Physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time"); we could use the metaphor of "large babushka" the famous "Russian doll" that comprises up to 5 or 7 smaller (same image but smaller dolls) contained within this "large babushka" doll! If we imagine a scenario in which this whole "large babushka doll" is created from "within- outwardly"; i.e., beginning with the innermost smallest babushka doll, and then covering an enlarging and encapsulating this "smallest babushka doll" within ever growing "babushka-dolls"! we can notice a surprising "finding" – i.e., that even though the "smallest babushka doll" cannot be seen when it is encapsulated by all of the "larger babushka dolls", when we focus on the "shape" of the "large babushka doll" – we suddenly realize that it is (in fact) the initial "shape" (and "characteristics") of the "small babushka doll" that actually "molded" (and in fact "determined") the "shape" (and characteristics) of the "large babushka doll"! This is because (we realize) that each successive "larger babushka doll" has to "conform" and "replicate" (while "enlarging") the "original small babushka doll's shape"! This metaphor implies that there is a greater strength to the initial letters of any object's name – relative to its subsequent letters, which "mold" the basic "characteristics" of the "spiritual facets" of this object, e.g., in consideration: both of the special ("spiritual") elements of each Hebrew letter and its associated semantic meaning/s, its Gimatria numeric value and its association with one of the five initial (Seven Secondary HCD's, listed above – with the former HCD's bearing a "greater weight" in molding the "spiritual characteristics" of the given object's later physical features)! Thus, for instance, the abovementioned Hebrew word "א-ד-ם" possesses the first letter as "א" which carries

out the "greatest weight" (e.g., alike the "smallest babushka" shaping the shape of the whole "big babushka doll" (subsequently)! This "א" Hebrew letter receives the Gimatria value of "1" – but this "1" digit can be viewed as representing the highest value of the "fifty zero's" (e.g., "possessing the value of many "trillions" of times per second – and indeed appearing in all of the "larger babushka dolls", that is "appearing in all of the fifty zero's UF's) This "א" letter also represents symbolically "G-D" as it is also the beginning of the word "G-D" in Hebrew: "אלוקים"! Finally, this first letter "א" is also associated with the first (Secondary Seven HCD's) of "Good-Will" implying that this "אדם" word signifies a great degree of "Divine-Good-Will"! In contrast, the second letter in this word "ד" has a higher Gimatria value of "4" and is associated with the second (of the Seven Secondary HCD's) which represents the "gevurah" the spiritual left side of "judgement" and "measurement" as signified by the "Multi-Spatial-Temporal Reservoir"... Interestingly the third letter is "ם" which has Gimatria numeric value of 40! and also represents the middle letter (or conjoining element) of the whole alphabet, with a special "spiritual" element of completion and wisdom (like

Moses' 40 days on Mt. Sinai at which he received the Holy Torah (Bible)! Interestingly also the combination of the two last letters are "ד-ם" semantic meaning is the Hebrew word for "blood"; so a partial understanding of the "spiritual nature" of the Hebrew word for a human-being points at it signifying a strong "Divine-Goo-Will" together with a "less-strong" (but still significant) element of "judgement", "bodily", "measured" elements – and the need (or efforts) to "combine" between these apparently "disparate" influences, alongside a strong element of "Wisdom" and "Perfection"! Another interesting point to note is that those "five zero's" allocated by the UCP's computation to the "length of time" and "order" in which the UCP computes each of these five (Seven Secondary HCD's) it is suggested – represents the fact that for each of these "five-template letters" takes into account each of the other four remaining letters and it affected by them (for each word, e.g., with shorter or longer words possibly missing or having redundant repetitions in terms of their usage of those five-template letter structure of the UCP's fifty zero's computation)!

Figure 5: UCR's Complete GDD, CMD, DEMP, Gim. THCD's

7). **Four Physical Features UCP's Computation**

The next phase or layer in the UCP's computation of all exhaustive objects involves the "translation" of the Seven Secondary HCD's & associated Gimatria's (e.g., of those five secondary HCD's) "spiritual nature" (described above) into the Four basic Physical Features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time")! Hence, the UCP translates each one of the five mentioned HCD's "spiritual nature" (e.g., associated with its specific HCD nature as well as the abovementioned Gimatria analysis etc. elements) into the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time"! As can be seen from the Diagram, once again the UCP's "allocation" of "four zero's" for each one of these five HCD's amounts in "twenty-zero's" is associated with this translation into the four basic physical features (of "space", "energy", "mas" and "time")!

8). **The UCP's "Infinite" – THCD's "Materialization" (6th Physical Feature: 47th-50th)**

The concluding phase of the UCP's computation of each exhaustive spatial pixel and object in the whole universe relates to the UCP's "materialization" of each object based on the sixth HCD of the "UCP's Actual Computed Object 4 Physical Features", which summates and cumulates all of the abovementioned 20 zero's HCD's four corresponding physical features input into the four general physical features for each exhaustive object which the UCP computes! It is important to note that given the almost "Infinite complexity" of the necessary computation for every exhaustive object (in the universe for every consecutive UF's frame/s) – not only in terms of the four physical features, but also taking into consideration the other (abovementioned) facets of the Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (e.g., including for instance the DEMP's need to "balance" and "correct" any "immoral action/s" made by any given individual human-being by producing the equivalent "negative situation" for that individual in order for him/her to make a sincere "teshuva"!)? Therefore, it is suggested that that the "Infinite" of the UCP (itself) is necessary and involved in the Tenth "UCP's Infinite Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Materialization! [47-50] in order to "materialize" any exhaustive object in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s)!

F) **"G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm**

One of the most fundamental changes that is brought about by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm is the key understanding that there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the "same" of "different" UF's frame/s)! This is simply due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels' (four associated basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") for each consecutive UF's frame/s and the complete "dissolution" of the whole universe (e.g., and all of its exhaustive spatial pixels "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s back into the singularity of the UCP)! As outlined previously, if the UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), then there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s (or relationship/s) between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (at any consecutive UF's frame/s)! Moreover, since all such exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe "dissolve" back into the singularity of this UCP ("in-between") any two consecutive UF's frame/s, therefore there also cannot exist any physical relationship/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels across any two ("consecutive" or even "non-consecutive" UF's frame/s)!

This profound new realization discovered through "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm undermines and negates the most basic "material-causal" assumption of the Old Paradigm: Thus, for instance the basic "Big-Bang" Model associated with the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of GRT was negated by "G-D's Physics" New

"A-Causal Computation" Paradigm! According to the "Big-Bang" Model, the whole creation of the entire physical universe was "caused" by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event which created all of the suns, galaxies, planets, space, time, energy and mass in the universe! But, since according to the New "A-Causal Computation" "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, the UCP's "simultaneously" computes all exhaustive spatial pixels (comprising any consecutive UF's frame/s), and the completely "dissolves" all such exhaustive spatial pixels (e.g., back into itself!) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s; therefore, there could not have existed any such (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical relationships between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising this (purely hypothetical) "Big-Bang" initial nuclear event! This is because there could not have existed any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising this (initially assumed) "Big-Bang" nuclear event (at any single or multiple UF's frame/s)!? And (anyway) the entire physical universe "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frames, so that there cannot "develop" any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any such (purely hypothetical initial) "Big-Bang" nuclear event and its creation of any "suns", "galaxies", "space", "mass" or "energy" etc.!?

G. **The "Infinitude Nature" of the "Universal Consciousness Reality"!**

We now come to a "pivotal transformative point" in Physics' basic understanding of the "Infinitude" of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which underlies – and in fact even "manifests" as the entire physical universe, but yet "transcends" it (i.e., "Infinitely"!)

This is because when we begin examining each of the multifarious facets of the UCR's continuous computation- "dissolution"- "sustenance"- and "development"- of each and every exhaustive spatial pixel/s comprising the entire physical universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s at the "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") towards this UCP's/UCR's "Ultimate Geulah Perfected Goal State"; we immediately realize that the only manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCR could continuously "compute", "dissolve", "sustain" and "develop" each and every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (simultaneously at the abovementioned incredible rate) – as "guided" by the UCP's/UCR's "Pre-planned Geulah Driven Blueprint Plan" is only based on this UCR's "Infinitude Nature"!

In order to elucidate this "Infinitude Nature" of this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR, let's focus (separately) upon each of the various facets of this UCP/UCR "Consistency Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" various derived computations that are all necessary in order to allow this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR to compute the next subsequent UF's frame/s (e.g., at this "incredible" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") (see Figure 1??) First, let's focus on the UCP's "Consistency-Gimatria" based computation of all exhaustive objects in the universe – for every consecutive UF's frame/s!?

As delineated in previous articles, "G-D's Physics" new understanding of the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR computes (simultaneously) all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame at the "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") – specifically in terms of its four basic physical features (e.g., of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") is derived from its "Gimatria" based computation of the five basic Hebrew letters' alphabetic-numeric value for each given object's Hebrew name (which alongside its "semantic" meaning, including "smaller" comprising semantic units or words contained within each given Hebrew name, as previously delineated); This is based upon the UCP's "infinitely complex" computation of those five basic (initially ordered) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (HCD's) of "Goodwill" (חסד), "Conscious-Moral Development" (CMD) ("גבורה"), "UNCIARE-JRH & DEMP" ("תפארה"), "UCP's Computed Potential Object" ("ניצח"), UCP's "Teshuva" ("היח") Gimatria based computation of the Four Physical Features (4PF'a):

Indeed, the UCP's/UCR's "Infinitude" - e.g., even only in terms of its computation of those "Gimatria" based computation of the five-basic (initial HCD's) template letters of each given Hebrew name, which is being translated into the Four Physical Features computation of the specific value/s (e.g., of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" for every exhaustive object in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s at the "unfathomable rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec!") in utterly "incomprehensible"! When we take into account the greater "infinite" complexity of the this UCP's/UCR's computation the "UCP's Consistency" other facets of the "Conscious-Moral Development", "Dynamic Equilibrium Principle" (DEP) and "Geulah Driven Development" - we cannot but stand "perplexed", "astonished" (and indeed at a great "awe"), when we consider the utter "Infinitude" of this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR! This is because we begin realizing that when we look at any of the "infinite" atoms, quarks etc. comprising any single or multiple object in the universe, as well as the whole vast and "infinite" regions of the universe's expanse; and we take into account that just for the "static" "existence" and "sustenance" of the universe and all of its multifarious "infinite" exhaustive spatial pixels - it is necessary for this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR "Infinitude" to compute each such exhaustive spatial pixel's "existence", "dissolution", "re-computation" (and "development") "simultaneously" at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec!

But, when we "add" into this "infinite computational complexity" the fact that each of these exhaustive spatial pixels is also undergoing a "continuous development" originated by this singular UCP/UCR - for instance, through the UCP's "CMD" involves a "Pre-planned Blueprint Plan" of the UCP that includes all of the universe's development - from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings: all assumed to have been computed and created in a mere "six days" (e.g., due to "G-D's Physics" Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) postulate and the universe's (otherwise "unexplained" "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion", previously delineated); and the whole of the universe's development throughout its "history" - leading up to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe, which Humanity (and Science in now entering with the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm), in which Science recognizes the singularity of the UCP/UCR, alongside its "intrinsic sublime characteristics" of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" etc. (which therefore affects and describes Humanity's "existence" and "behavior"! If we are just to "imagine" the "infinite complexity" of the UCP's "Pre-planned Blueprint Plan" of the whole development of the universe's history including its "macroscopic development" from "inanimate": matter, through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, and also its unique "specific objects' development" (pattern/s): Thus, for instance, we know that each unique "object", i.e., whether it be "inanimate matter" (of any specific type: atoms, subatomic particles, chemical compounds etc.) or even more so: "animate": plants, animals or human-beings possesses a unique characteristic for its "life-span development"! This means, that the UCP's "infinitely complex" computation of all "animate": plants, animals, and human-beings (e.g., "simultaneously" throughout Earth's different environments etc.) must "remember", "sustain", "dissolve" and "re-compute" and "develop" each particular Biological specie - based on its specific pattern of development across its full life-span, i.e., for an unfathomable number of Biological species and specific organisms (plants, animals or human-beings)!?

We must bear in mind that not only has the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm proven empirically to more valid than the Old "Material-Causal" (e.g., based upon the direct empirical validation of G-D's Physics above-mentioned two unique "Critical Predictions" as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's & QM's predictions!); but more fundamentally, the basic "Material-Causal" assumption of the Old Paradigm, e.g., assuming that everything in the uni-

verse (either at the "macroscopic" Relativistic level or at the "microscopic subatomic" levels) operates based on (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between a (finite) number of constituting material elements - was principally negated both based upon "G-D's Physics' New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm, which asserts that there cannot exist any such (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the "same" - or "different" - UF's frame/s, e.g., due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any consecutive UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels back into the singularity of this singular UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! In addition, "G-D's Physics" discovery of the (profound) "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) was (previously) shown (more fundamentally) to "principally negate" the very basic "Computational Structure" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm! This is because this (novel) CDP indicated that underlying this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm there exists a basic "Self-Referential Computational System" Computational Structure which inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational indeterminacy" that are contradicted through the CDP - i.e., instead leading to the inevitable recognition of the singular higher-ordered UCP which (alone) can simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s!

So, we reach the inevitable conclusion wherein the basic "Material-Causal" assumption of the Old Paradigm must be strictly negated (e.g., as shown above and previously, due to "G-D's Physics' New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm and its novel CDP theoretical postulate) - in favor of the CDP's discovered (and empirically validated) identification of the singular higher-ordered UCP's continuous (simultaneous) "computation" - "dissolution" - "re-computation" - and "development" of all exhaustive spatial pixels (e.g., comprising the entire physical universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s at the "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$!) This means that as we've begun seeing (above) the UCP's (simultaneous) computation of all "inanimate" and particularly "animate": plants, animals and human-beings involves an "Infinitude" of its computational complexity: to "remember", "sustain", "dissolve" and then "re-compute" and "develop" every exhaustive spatial pixel's four basic physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" values) for each individual plant, animal and human-being (simultaneously at this "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$!) In other words, since according to "G-D's Physics' New (empirically validated) New Scientific Paradigm, this singular higher-ordered UCP has "Pre-planned" the "Blueprint Plan" for the universe's entire development - e.g., from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings (i.e., as mentioned above and delineated previously occurring within the UCP's "Six Days Creation Model" due to the CHCF postulate and the Hubble Tension's otherwise "unexplained" phenomenon!?) also "guides" the UCP's computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s, as can be seen from Figure 1 and Diagram 1; that the UCP's computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s is dependent upon the "Three Initial Key" (TIK) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (HCD's), in which the whole development of the entire physical universe has been "Pre-planned" (from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, as mentioned above), which is also executed through the UCP's "Consistency" computation's (abovementioned) "Conscious-Moral Development"! This means that the UCP has to simultaneously compute "anew" for each consecutive UF's frame/s all "inanimate" matter's composition, i.e., once again: "remember", "sustain", "dissolve", "re-compute" and "develop" each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, in terms of its four basic physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time"); and even exponentially more "infinitely complex" is the UCP's computation of every exhaustive "animate" object - based on its (abovementioned "Gimatria" alphabetic numeric translation into those Four basic Physical Features) and the "Infinitude" of the UCP's computation of every specific animate enti-

ty: particular plant (e.g., including the vast differences between an algae and say a huge Sequoia Tree!), every exhaustive Biological animal species and every individual human-being – in terms of their particular "life-span development" characteristics at every "trillionth of a trillionth etc." (e.g., " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}!$ ")

Indeed, our recognition of the utter "Infinite" (capacities) of this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR becomes even more apparent when we add into our understanding of the manner in which this UCP/UCR computes, sustains and develops the entire physical universe – the (abovementioned) "UCP's Consistency – DEMP" computation! This is because (as previously delineated) the UCP's DEMP essentially implies that (due to the UCP's "intrinsic-sublime" "All-Goodness" and "Moral" characteristic), the UCP's DEMP "balances" and "enhances" any given individual human-being's "moral-choice/s" – leading Humanity towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal", e.g., by "teaching" each individual human-being that it is truly "inseparable" from the "Oneness", "Peace", "Morality" and "All-Goodness" of this singular higher-ordered UCP! The UCP accomplishes this "Ultimate Geulah Perfected Goal" through the DEMP's "balancing" of any individual human-being's selection of ("G-D forbid") "immoral action/s" towards another human-being instigated through the UCP's selection of an "equivalent-negative" situation in which that individual human being who ("G-D forbid") inflicted "pain"/"suffering" upon another individual human-being will have to experience the same "negative situation", so that he/she may make a sincere "teshuva", e.g., real "remorse" over the "wrong-doing" or "immoral action" they've done. Conversely, if any individual human-being have opted to "assist" or (otherwise) "act-morally" towards another individual human-being, then equally this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR will select an "equivalently-positive" situation, in which this "assisting" (moral-actioned) individual human-being will also have the "privilege" of experiencing such an "equivalently-positive" situation in which (most likely) that "other human-being" which he/she assisted will assist or bestow "goodness" upon himself/herself? As delineated previously, the manner in which this UCP's DEMP "operates" is based upon the existence of the UCP's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" comprising all possible "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" or each individual human-being (possessing a free moral choice)! This implies that this singular higher-ordered UCP has to compute for each individual human-being (at any "trillionth of a trillionth of a second etc.") the precise "situation" would allow that particular individual human-being to experience the "same" ("negative" or "positive" situation/s) in which that individual human-being ("G-D forbid") inflicted "pain/suffering" upon another human-being, so that this "negative-immoral situation" will lead that individual human-being to undertake a sincere "teshuva" (e.g., deep "remorse" and conscious decision not to repeat any such "wrong-doing"! But, this means that this singular (higher-ordered) UCP/UCR has to (simultaneously) compute for each of the over eight Billion individual human-beings (existing today) the DEMP's "balancing" of all of their previous "moral/immoral action/s" taken throughout their lives – while taking into consideration all of the "other human-beings" that were involved in their "moral/immoral action/s" at any point/s in time in their lives, and consequently compute (at the "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}!$ ") every consecutive UF's frame/s that would "balance" any "immoral action/s" (e.g., acted upon "against" any specific individual human-being) by creating the same "equivalent negative" situation (e.g., most likely by "reversing" the situation so that the "injured other person" will "reproduce" the same "negative situation" so as to have the "injuring person" experience "G-D forbid" the same "negative-immoral" situation, or by "reinforcing" and "remunerating" any "positive moral-action" by any Individual human being (towards another human being) which necessitates the UCP's "reinforcement" or "remuneration" of this "positive-moral action" of that individual human being through the UCP's computation of all those "equivalent positive situation/s" in which the "good-moral actor" (human-being) is being "rewarded" (or "encouraged"/"remunerated") for his/her "right-moral choice"! In both cases, it is

likely that the UCP's/UCR's "simultaneous" computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s will compute the "Infinitely complex" (abovementioned) "moral-balancing" for each individual human-being – i.e., as "coupled" with those particular individual human-being/s that he or she have acted in a "moral" or "immoral" manner at each "(minimal) time-point" along the course of their entire live/s, in order to compute (e.g., create) the "equivalently-positive/negative" situation (i.e., with those particular individual human-beings which that given individual human-being interacted (in a "positive"- or "negative" – moral action/s), in order to "morally-balance" or "morally enhance" each individual human-being (out of the over eight Billion individual human-beings living on the Planet Earth)!?)

If this is not "infinitely-complex"(enough), we must take into consideration the significance of the UCP's "teshuva" HCD's which allows for each (such) Individual human-being to make a sincere "teshuva" (as explained above) in which case the UCP will "avert" and "omit" the UCP's (preceding) "Computed Potential Object" ("גזח") – i.e., "equivalent negative situation" UF's situation, for each individual human-being (e.g., with his/her "coupled other human-being" towards which the "immoral action" was conducted, "G-D forbid")! Indeed, it is utterly "amazing" and "awe-inspiring" to realize the UCP's/UCR's "Infinite" – having to compute not only the "infinitely complex" computation for each of Humanity's (eight Billion human-beings), but also to take into consideration within this "Infinite" of the UCP's computation also the degree to which each of these (eight Billion individual human-beings) has undertaken a sincere "teshuva" (towards any single or multiple other individual human-beings), and the manner in which this "Infinitely complex" UCP's computation alters the UCP's "Computed Potential Object's" (e.g., potentially "equivalent negative situation" into an "equivalent positive situation") for the subsequent "Actual Computed Object" HCD's for each individual human being (out of the over eight Billion individual human-beings!) Indeed, according to "G-D's Physics" (empirically validated) New Scientific Paradigm, due to this "Infinite" complexity of the UCP's/UCR's simultaneous computation of the DEMP – for each of the over eight Billion Individual human-beings (living today on our Planet), the direct involvement of this "Infinite UCR/UCP" in executing the actual "materialization" of the next subsequent UF's frame (e.g., at the "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}!$ ") at the tenth HCD's of the "UCP's Infinite Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions".

H. Earth's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) Functional Epicenter of the Universe!

One of the key differences between the New (empirically validated) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm and the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm is the "Centrality of Human Consciousness" – i.e., in "space" and "time", and its intimate connection with the "Universal Consciousness Reality's" (UCR's) "Geulah Driven Universe" (GDU)! This is because according to "G-D's Physics" New (empirically proven) Scientific Paradigm, it seems that "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) plays a major role in the "Universe's Increase its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE)! As we've already seen, there is clear (and direct) empirical evidence for the centrality of this CHCF in terms of its UNCIARE's acceleration in the universe! As outlined above, in contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" concept (e.g., which has been negated both based on the experimental failure to detect its existence experimentally, and "G-D's Physics" principle computational negation of its associated Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's SRCS Computational Structure!) – which assumes that this (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" concept can only account for a "constant-rate" expansion rate of the universe; the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm points at an increase in the rate of the universe's expansion, e.g., "UNCIARE" due to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus", which occurs during the Jewish Rosh Hashanah's (two days' special) time-interval! Indeed, it has been proven empirically (above) that it is solely based on

this CHCF that the universe's rate of expansion" increases over time", e.g., as indicated by the (otherwise unexplained) "Universe's Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" ("Hubble's Tension")!; An even more direct (further) validation of the centrality of the CHCF was called for Astronomers to validate during the upcoming two days' Jewish Rosh Hashanah – during September 16th & 17th 2023, in which it is predicted that the universe's rate of expansion will significantly increase (and continue to increase) during the whole ensuing Jewish year), relative to the universe's measured rate of expansion in the preceding time prior to Sep. 16-17th! Moreover, previously it's been shown that this same CHCF may be responsible for the Centrality of Human Consciousness – not just in "time" but also in "space"! This relates to the otherwise "unexplained" empirically validated phenomenon wherein the Astronomical measurement of the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion (UARE) also indicates that planet Earth stands at the center of this UARE! In other words, it may be the case wherein the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion – i.e., related to "space", wherein it is only relative to planet Earth's position that this accelerated rate of expansion pertaining to the furthest regions of space (wherein the farther any galactic element exists relative to planet Earth the faster its measured acceleration would be)! If (for instance) it is found that such equivalent Astronomical measurements of the UARE – do not yield the same "symmetrical increase" in the universe's UARE then this would validate the centrality of planet Earth (and its associated centrality of this CHCF) – in "space", as well as in "time"! "G-D's Physics" Novel CHCF's Center of the Universe Hypothesis! We therefore reach an "astounding" new Hypothesis of "G-D's Physics", i.e., hypothesizing that at the center of the universe's existence, dynamics and development – stand our planet Earth due to this CHCF, including the rotation of our sun (around it) and the accelerated expansion of other galactic elements "emanating" from planet Earth's CHCF! This is because once we realize that the evolution of the physical universe cannot be explained merely due to an any initially assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear event- e.g., based on the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm (above); and that (in fact), the basic SRCS Computational Structure of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm was shown to be negated by "G-D's Physics" (novel) "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) – i.e., as inevitably leading to both "logical-inconsistency" and (ensuing) "computational indeterminacy" that are both negated by the CDP's insistence upon the (proven) capacity of this apparently SRCS Computational System to determine the accelerated expansion of the universe – which (according to the CDP) points at the singularity of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/ Consciousness Principle" (UCP) as simultaneously computing all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s)! And most significantly, empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" (above) unique "Critical Prediction" regarding the "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) – as more valid than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's assumed "constant rate" of the universe's expansion rate! Therefore, we must negate (and reject) the Old "Material-Causal" GRT's Paradigm's assumption wherein the entire physical universe has been created (or "caused") by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear even, and that its accelerated rate of expansion can be explained through the (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" concept (which has been negated based on the three abovementioned considerations)!? The alternative (novel) explanation offered by the New (empirically validated) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm for the origination- sustenance- and development- of the whole physical universe is solely based on the operation of the singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) that (solely) exists both "during" its computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s (as solely responsible for the computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel's its four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time"!); And specifically, as associated with this UCP's connection with the CHCF – which brings about the UCP's initiation of the UNCIARE (empirically validated) phenomenon! In other words, the

UNCIARE empirically validated phenomenon (unequivocally) proves that the origination of the entire physical universe, and its accelerated rate of expansion (e.g., as indicated "Hubble Tension") is brought about by the UCP's consecutive computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s – and specifically by the CHCF's UNCIARE increase in the rate of the universe's expansion, e.g., assumed to take place at every Annual "Jewish Rosh-Hashanah" two days' time-interval (i.e., this year this will take place during Sep. 16-17th 2023 and onwards in which it is predicted the rate of the universe's expansion will increase significantly, relative to the rate of the universe's expansion prior to the 16-17th – which I've called Astronomers and Cosmologists to test experimentally!) Indeed, once we realize that the entire physical universe "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s and that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in any single- or multiple- UF's frame/s; and therefore that the only "force" that creates- "dissolves"- re-creates- and evolves- any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe is this singular higher-ordered UCP; hence, based on the clear empirical evidence indicating an UNCIARE increase in the rate of the universe's expansion associated with the CHCF (hypothesized to take place during the Jew Rosh Hashanah!) we reach the inevitable theoretical conclusion wherein the expansion of the entire physical universe depends upon the CHCF – which brings about this UNCIARE increase in the universe's expansion rate (beginning in each Jewish Rosh Hashanah and continuing throughout the entire subsequent Jewish Year). We therefore reach the inevitable conclusion wherein taking together these two empirically validated facts: a) Empirical Validation of "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE (annual) increase in the rate of the universe's expansion, which according to G-D's Physics is associated with the CHCF (e.g., specifically during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashanah" special two days' time interval, as noted above: a call for Astronomers/Cosmologists to test this UNCIARE-JRH during the upcoming Sep. 16th-17th, 2023 & onwards!) In other words, this UNCIARE (JRH) empirically confirmed phenomenon points at the centrality of CHCF "in time", i.e., specifically during the JRH (e.g., to be directly confirmed through the above call for Astronomers/Cosmologists to test during the upcoming JRH!) b) Centrality of Earth's CHCF for the Universe's Observed Accelerated Rate of Expansion! The empirically observed "unexplained" "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion") "Hubble Tension" (indicates that the rate of the universe's expansion has increased (significantly) from its early "Background Radiation" stage to the current (increased) rate in the universe's expansion! This phenomenon is associated with Planet Earth's "Epicenter" of the universe – in "space" (e.g., based on the fact that the accelerated rate of our regions of the universe is proportional to the distance from "Earth")! Taken together, these empirically validated (major otherwise "unexplained") phenomena point at the centrality of Earth's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" – in "space" and "time": as the (functional) center of the universe! It also reinforces the singularity of the higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" as the sole source "originating" the entire physical universe (at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec')!

I. "G-D's Physics" Redefinition of the Universe's Four Physical Features as Part of a "Geulah-Driven Development" Universe!

We thus reach the culmination of this "Synopsis" of "G-D's Physics" Redefinition of the Universe's Four (basic) Physical Features – based on "G-D's Physics" profound new understanding of both the "true nature" of the entire physical universe – which is the singular ("computationally-invariant") "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR or UCP), e.g., that exists both "during" its (simultaneous) computation of each consecutive UF's frame/s (exhaustive spatial pixels), as well as (solely exists) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (without the presence of any physical universe!); And of the "Geulah Driven Development" (GDD) "steering" the entire physical universe (e.g., by this singular higher-ordered UCR) towards its

Indeed, our whole understanding of the "origin"- "sustenance"- "development"- and "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of the universe changes ("dramatically") based on "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" (empirically validated) Scientific Paradigm; this is because in contrast to the Old "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) Paradigm underlying both General Relativity Theory" (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) which assumed that every phenomenon (or entity) in the universe can be explained merely based on (direct or indirect) physical interaction/s between a "finite" set of material entities, e.g., such as for instance the "creation" of the entire physical universe – which is assumed to be "caused" by an initial "nuclear event" (which is assumed to have created all of the suns, galaxies, mass and energy in the universe); the New "A-Causal Computation" "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm (for Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics) asserts that since this singular (higher-ordered) UCP/UCR "simultaneously" computes every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s; and all of these exhaustive spatial pixels "dissolve" back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s), there cannot exist any such (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" (random) physical interaction/s at any given (single or multiple) UF's frame/s! Instead, the whole composition of the entire physical universe – including every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising it, is solely computed by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR for each consecutive UF's frame/s! Moreover, as shown (above and previously), based on those two (novel and profound) "Computational Invariance Principle" and "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) theoretical postulates of "G-D's Physics" New (empirically validated) Scientific Paradigm we begin understanding that the physical universe – does not exist as an "independent-solid" reality, but rather only exists as a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality", which solely exists "continuously", "uniformly" and "invariantly" both "during" its computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s, and also exists (without the presence of any physical universe!) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Therefore, we realized that the only manner in which the universe "exists" (e.g., apparently "continuously"!) is based on the "incessant" computation of this singular higher-ordered UCR/UCP! But, this profound new realization also pushed us to examine the basic (profound) characteristics of this singular UCR, i.e., its "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (THCD's) and associated "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) – which integrates (for the first time in Physics) between the Four basic Physical Features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") within a singular formula! Succinctly stated, this new THCD's UCF points at the UCP's/UCR's continuous "steering" of the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State, i.e., in which all of Humanity will recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR, alongside its profound characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" (thereby affecting and characterizing Humanity's behavior and existence!)

J. A "Geulah-Driven" Space-Time Evolution of the Universe!

Hence, the alternative theoretical explanation offered by "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm for the origination- sustenance- evolution- and indeed the "Ultimate Goal" of the entire physical universe's development is given through "G-D's Physics" newly discovered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP or UCR), and its associated THCD-UCF! Perhaps another "Solomon's Temple Blueprint Plan" Metaphor may be helpful, in order to illustrate the (possible) manner according to which this singular (higher-ordered) UCR has "preplanned" the entire origination- sustenance- and evolution- of the entire physical universe: from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings – towards the fulfillment of the "Perfected Ultimate Geulah Goal", in which Science and Humanity (more generally) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, e.g., including its intrinsic characteristics of "Morality", "Peace"

According to this "Solomon's Temple Blueprint Plan" Metaphor, King Solomon had to "preplan" the whole design and build-up of the (immaculate) Temple from its "Completed-Perfected-Final" stage – "backwards" towards the initial stages of its construction, so that this "Blueprint Plan" will lead up to this "Completed-Perfected-Final" state of the Temple! (We could not imagine a scenario in which King Solomon's builders begin "constructing" this Immaculate Temple – without such a "perfected Blueprint Plan", i.e., just by "experimenting" with different stones with no "preplanned Blueprint Plan" for its orderly completion?!) Equivalently, "G-D's Physics" New (Twenty-First Century's) "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm postulates that this singular higher-ordered UCR has "preplanned" a "Blueprint Plan" – from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards" towards the initial stages of "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, and up to the "Perfected Geulah State" of the universe in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of this UCR! Indeed, once we fully realize that there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any two (consecutive or even non-consecutive UF's frame/s), we come to the inevitable conclusion wherein the entire evolution of the whole universe cannot be "caused" by any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between certain "massive" objects and their (assumed) "curvature" of "Space-Time" (or the corresponding determination of the "travelling pathways" of these "massive" or other "less-massive" objects as "caused" by this assumed "curved Space-Time" fabric), as GRT postulated! Instead, we realize that according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, the whole universe is being continuously "created", "dissolved", "re-created" and "evolved" so many "trillions" of time each second –by this singular UCR! Moreover, we realize that the sole manner in which the entire physical universe evolves, is based on this preplanned "Blueprint Plan" of advancing the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah-Goal" State! Indeed, we currently stand at a "historic time", e.g., equivalent perhaps to Eddington's empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" of Mercury's "double-valued" perihelion's curvature around the Sun – with the empirical validation of two such (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's & QM's Models! Moreover, this empirical validation of those two (unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – in fact, point at the attainment of Humanity's (and Science's) "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State! This is because the very definition of this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of Humanity and the Universe is precisely one in which Humanity recognizes the singular reality of this UCR, i.e., underlying (and transcending) the entire physical universe, and being characterized through its basic intrinsic properties of: "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" – which will also characterize ("guide" and "typify") Humanity's newly "Perfected Geulah State"!

We therefore begin realizing that the whole "origination"- "sustenance"- and "development" of the entire physical universe is driven by this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which has "preplanned" the whole development of the entire physical universe in order to reach that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" of the universe, in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, alongside its "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"! We realize that since the UCP is the sole "computationally-invariant" Principle (or "reality") that can "produce"- "sustain"- "dissolve"- or "evolve" any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, as well as "originate"- "sustain" and "evolve" the entirety of the physical universe! And moreover, since that the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR is continuously "originating"- "evolving"- ("dissolving"-) and "developing" the entire physical universe – is "motivated" by this singular higher-or

dered UCP's/UCR's intrinsic "sublime characteristics" of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony", and geared towards fulfilling the Universe's "Ultimate Geulah Perfected Goal" State of the Universe (and of Humanity)! Therefore, we are "astonished" to find out that at every "trillionth-of-trillionth etc." of a second (e.g., " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{-50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") this UCP computes and evolves every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe – including all human-beings, animals, plants and even "inanimate matter" based upon the UCP's THCD's (and associated THCD's-UCF!) which is "steering" the universe (and Humanity) towards that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State, in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR and begin living in accordance with this UCP's/UCR's "sublime" characteristics of "Morality", "All-Goodness", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

The important point to be noted (here) is that we begin noticing that the manner in which this UCP computes- sustains- ("dissolves"-) and evolves- every exhaustive spatial pixel (as well as the entirety of the whole universe) relies upon its THCD's extremely rapid computation, e.g., at the rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{-50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ " in which the "Human Collective Consciousness Focus" (as well as the Individual Human Consciousness Moral Choice/s) plays a key central role, alongside this singular higher-ordered UCP's "steering" of Humanity and the Universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State"! This is because, when we closely examine those THCD's we notice two very important elements:

a) The sixth Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of the Universe's Expansion (NCARUE) at the Jewish Rosh Hashanah (JRH) – determines the universe's increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion, i.e., beginning at each JRH's two days' special time-interval! (This year the UNCIARE-JRH took place during Oct., 3rd-4th, 2024, for which there was an urgent Call for Astronomers to validate the increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion beginning in these two days and subsequently, relative to the rate of the universe's expansion prior to these two days' JRH time-interval! Data is still missing regarding this urgent call for Astronomers/Cosmologists to validate this year's Sep. 16-17th UNCIARE.) Nevertheless, one of the two unique "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – which have been empirically validated as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM is this UNCIARE (JRH) Critical Prediction! As shown above, this "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE (JRH) "Critical Prediction" was validated empirically based on the "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (CAGUARE or as it is generally called: "Hubble Tension") which supports "G-D's Physics" annual increase at the JRH's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) two days' time-interval! Indeed, such a "**Hubble Tension**" cannot be accounted for GRT's "constant-rate" expansion of the universe due to the (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter"/"Dark-Energy" concepts – but precisely confirms "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE "Critical Prediction"! This is because based on "G-D's Physics" CHCF postulate which takes place every consecutive JRH's (two days' time interval and remains constant throughout the whole subsequent Jewish Year) it is expected that the universe's expansion rate will increase "over time", i.e., leading to the observed "Hubble Tension" which is explained by "G-D's Physics" stipulated UNCIARE-JRH phenomenon!

b) Earth's CHCF "Functional Center" of the Universe – In "Space" & "Time"!

Indeed, the existence of "Hubble's Law" (HL), e.g., indicating that the rate of the universe's expansion – relative to "Earth's Functional Epicenter" increases as a function of the distance of any give galaxy from "Earth's Functional Epicenter" points at Earth functioning as the "Universe's Functional Epicenter"! Moreover, when we take into consideration the combination of HL's Earth's Functional Center together with the (abovementioned) "**Hubble Tension**" UNCIARE-JRH we must reach the inevitable conclusion

wherein Earth's CHCF stands at the basis of Earth's Functional Center – i.e., both in "space" and "time"! In other words, the clear empirical evidence positioning Earth as the "Functional Center" of the universe, as evidenced by HL & associated "**Hubble Tension**" as explained through "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH indicate that Earth's CHCF is responsible for Earth's UNCIARE-JRH increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion (e.g., every consecutive Jewish Year), and when taken together with HL indicate that Earth's CHCF serves as the "Functional Center" of the entire physical universe both in "space" and "time"!

c) The UCP's "Non-Continuous Computation of the Universe" (UCP-NC-CU)!

The next "step" in our new understanding of the fundamental "metamorphosis" that "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm creates in our basic understanding of the true "origin", "sustenance" and "development" of the entire physical universe is associated with "G-D's Physics" other unique "Critical Prediction" validation, e.g., associated with the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings! According to "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, the UCP's computation of the entire physical universe (as well as of any of its multifarious exhaustive spatial pixels) is "non-continuous", i.e., existing only "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s, but "dissolving" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two subsequent UF's frame/s (e.g., therefore the whole physical universe has been redefined as representing only a "computationally-variant" manifestation of the singular "computationally-invariant" UCP which exists "constantly, continuously and uniformly" both "during" its computation of each consecutive UF's frame/s, and also solely existing without the presence of any physical universe "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s!) Indeed, "G-D's Physics" (second) "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings' unique "Critical Prediction" – differentially predicted this "Proton Radius Puzzle" key findings, wherein the relatively "more massive" Muon particle would be computed by the UCP as more "spatially-consistent" than the relatively "less-massive" electron particle (across a series of UF's frame/s)! This is because according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm the UCP's computation of any given particle's "mass" value is based on the UCP's "Object-consistent" computation of each given particle – i.e., with more massive particles being computed as more "spatially-consistent" (as outlined previously) This leads to the UCP's computation of the relatively "more massive" Muon particle as being more "spatially-consistent" than the less-massive electron particle, which then leads to the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings of the relatively "smaller, more accurate measurements" of the Hydrogen's Proton Radius – when encircled by the relatively "more massive" Muon particle, than when encircled by the "standard electron" particle! But, implied within this empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" unique "Proton-Radius Puzzle" "Critical Prediction" is the realization that the UCP's computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the entire physical universe) – is "non-continuous", i.e., "dissolving" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Indeed, as indicated above, "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – negates the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in either the "same"- or "different" UF's frame/s, which also implies that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) physical interactions between any two consecutive UF's frame/s!

As shown above, "G-D's Physics" two profound "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" theoretical postulates indicated that the only manner in which the "computationally-variant" universe is "originated", ("dissolved"), "sustained" and "developed" – at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{-50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ " is based upon the UCP's THCD's-UCF, which has "pre-planned" the whole development of the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate matter" through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards reaching the uni

verse's "Ultimate Perfected Geulah" State of the universe, in which both Humanity and Science will recognize the singularity of this UCP, alongside its "sublime" characteristics of "Morality", "All-Goodness", "Peace" & "Harmony"!

Since the UCP's "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe relates to Humanity's attainment of such a "Perfected Geulah State", in which all human-beings realize their "oneness" with this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR, i.e., including their realization of the UCP's basic fundamental "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle": which "teaches" every individual human-being to regard any other human-being as "integral inseparable parts" of this same singular higher-ordered UCP, therefore we see that the UCP's execution of every consecutive UF's exhaustive spatial pixels – strongly relates to its computation of each individual human-being's Moral Choice/s at every "minimal time-point", including the (previously delineated) possibility of "Teshuvah" (e.g., corresponding to the UCP's eighth "Teshuva" HCD, which allows every human-being to carry out a sincere "Teshuvah" remorse and conscious decision to not repeat any specific immoral action); which then alters and changes the UCP's computation of the subsequent (ninth) "UCP's Actual Computed Object", (i.e., in terms of "avoiding" and "altering" that individual human-being's next subsequent UF's frame/s presentation of an "equivalent negative situation" in which that individual human-being would have to experience the same "negative immoral situation" which he/she inflicted pain/suffering upon any other individual human-being – since that individual human-being has carried out a genuine "teshuvah" regarding his/her "immoral choice/s")! So, we can see that at the very center of the UCP's continuous creation- sustenance- and development- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the entire physical universe's development) stands the UCP's consideration of the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) – at the JRH's two-days' time-interval, which brings about the "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCI-ARE), as well as the UCP's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle which affects that UCP's computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel (in any subsequent UF's frame/s of the universe), and advances the whole of Humanity towards that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of Humanity and the Universe!

K. Plausibility of "G-D's Physics" New "Universe's Seven Days Origination Model" (USDOM)

It is important to note (on a philosophical-scientific level) that since the actual capacity of Science (or Physics) to carry out any direct measurement of the "origination" of the universe – is strictly negated by GRT, due to the fact that we cannot move at a speed exceeding the "Speed of Light" (and therefore cannot "move back in time" to directly observe the actual "origination" of the universe!) therefore, we can only "contrast" between different Scientific Paradigms – such as the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (underlying GRT's "Big-Bang" Model) and the New "G-D's Physics", and consequently decide which of these Scientific Paradigms prevails! Significantly, the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm has been proven to be "more valid" than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (underlying both GRT & QM) based on the empirical validation of its two unique "Critical Predictions" – e.g., associated with the "Proton Radius Puzzle" findings and the UNCIARE (JRH)! Hence, the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's "Big-Bang" Model was negated based on "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, and therefore its THCD's-UCF theoretical explanation of the continuous "origination", "dissolution" "sustenance", and "development" of the entire physical universe – towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" must be accepted, including its corresponding stipulation of the USDOM's "seven days creation" of the entirety of the universe (e.g., with all "inanimate" and "animate" forms including human-beings!) Indeed, a further (even more direct) empirical validation (previously called for Astronomers to carry out) that would test for the appearance of the relatively "more

massive" Muon particle in a greater number of "Fine-Temporal Measurements" (FTM) in a greater number of UF's than the equivalent (negatively charged) electron particle would directly validate the ongoing continuous computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe by this singular higher-ordered UCP, e.g., giving further support for "G-D's Physics" stipulated (novel) "UCP's Seven Day Creation Model" (UCP-SDCM)!

Over and beyond the clear (abovementioned) validation of two unique "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM, which forces Science to accept "G-D's Physics" as the New Twenty-first Century (valid) Scientific Paradigm, there are several further supporting elements taken from "G-D's Physics" "internal-validity" also pointing at the plausibility of its USDOM of the origination, as part of the basic "Geulah Perfected State Driven Universe" new understanding of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm!

a) It is clear that the universe could not be caused by the initially assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear event, nor could its accelerated rate of expansion could be accounted for by the purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts, nor through Einstein's Equations' three EEE's (as negated by "G-D's Physics" CDP)!

b) Moreover, based on "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" New Scientific Paradigm (as noted above) due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s, we reached the inevitable conclusion that the universe cannot evolve based on any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s), and therefore that the only "viable means" for explaining the origination- sustenance- "dissolution"- re-computation- and development of the entire physical universe (or of any of its multifarious exhaustive spatial pixels) can only be given based on the analysis of the singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR that is continuously "originating" – "dissolving" "re-creating" and "evolving" every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec!")

c) The complete "dependence" – and in fact "inseparability" of the entire physical universe from this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR is significantly strengthened based on the (abovementioned) profound "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" theoretical postulates – which indicates that there exist only this one singular reality, which is this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR or UCP) that exists both "during" its (simultaneous) computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s, and also solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Indeed, according to these two (profound) theoretical postulates the entire physical universe (and all of its exhaustive spatial pixels) does not exist "independently" of this singular UCR – but rather merely represents a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular UCR reality!

d) Hence, we realize that the whole existence- (continuous) origination- sustenance- and development- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe totally depends upon the "intrinsic characteristics" of this singular UCR/UCP, which were discovered as the UCP's "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (THCD's), alongside the UCP THCD's Universal Computational Formula: as noted above (and previously), these UCP's THCD's and (associated) UCF – all point at "G-D's Physics" "Geulah Driven Universe"! In other words, these UCP's THCD's point at the UCP's "Pre-planned Blueprint Plan" for advancing the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings leading to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state of Humanity and the universe!

e) Indeed, according to "G-D's Physics" "Reversed Time Geulah Goal" postulate, the whole "origination"- "sustenance"- and "development" of the entire physical universe has been "pre-planned" by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR from its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR and its "sublime" characteristics (e.g., THCD's) specifically leading to the universe's "Ultimate Geulah Perfected State" of "Peace", "Harmony", "Morality" and "All-Goodness" (which will therefore also characterize Humanity's Geulah State and accompanying behavior!)

f) When taken together with the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) "Critical Prediction" increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion stipulated to occur during the two days' Jewish "Rosh Hashanah" (New Year) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) – which was empirically supported based on the observed (and otherwise "unexplained" "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" [Hubble Tension]); and more specifically, the current call for Astronomers & Cosmologists to empirically validate a more direct "Critical Prediction" of "G-D's Physics" regarding the UNCIARE's increased rate of the universe's expansion predicted to take place during the upcoming JRH Oct. 3rd-4th 2024 (e.g., relative to prior to Oct. 3rd-4th 2024, and carry over in an increased universe's accelerated rate of expansion throughout the whole subsequent Jewish Year!) These results clearly indicate that the empirically validate "Hubble Tension" (supporting "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE "Critical Prediction", as explained above and previously) supports "G-D's Physics" centrality of the CHCF as key in explaining the UNCIARE increase in the universe's rate of expansion over the course of the universe's development course (rather than "G-D's Physics" negated purely hypothetical "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" or any of Einstein's other tree EEE's, as described above)

g) This means that presence of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) must have existed from the initial "origination" of the universe by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR! Specifically, when taken together with the UNCIARE-JRH indication that this empirically validated UNCIARE may take place during the JRH's two days' time interval then this implies that from the "first year" of the universe's "origination" by the UCP/UCR, there must have existed this UNCIARE-JRH's CHCF that allowed the (initial) "accelerated expansion rate of the universe! This implies that from the universe's "origination point" by the UCP, shortly after its initial origination, there must have occurred this CHCF JRH UNCIARE phenomenon!

h) When taken together with "G-D's Physics" THCD's UCF (precise) description of the manner in which the UCP accurately computes each subsequent UF's (e.g., at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec") based primarily upon the UCP's (consecutive) computation of the "seven secondary HCD's" (as "preplanned" and "executed" by the UCP's Three Key Initial HCD's Blueprint Plan for steering the universe from its inanimate through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State") – then this suggests as "plausible" and "reasonable" that the UCP's initial "origination" of the entire physical universe – from its initial "inanimate" state through its pre-planned subsequent "animate": plants, animals and human-beings (and even perhaps initial recognition by a human-being of the singularity of this UCP, i.e., "G-D" Presence) may have occurred during the first seven days – one day for each of these secondary seven HCD's! Subsequently, after this "first week" in which all "animate" and "animate" (plants, animals and human-beings) have been "originated" by the UCP/UCR, it is suggested that the first CHCF JRH-UNCIARE occurred which allowed for the UCP's first UNCIARE-JRH increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion! Hence, it's become clear that Science (and Humanity) have now reached a "critical turning point" in its development: instead of Science's "lifelong" basic "Material-Causal" assumption (e.g., including even "Newtonian Classical Mechanics") wherein it was assumed that everything in the universe can be explained as being "caused" by a certain "material-causal" (di-

rect or indirect) physical interactions between any given (finite(number of material elements!)? Such as GRT's basic assumption, wherein the origination of the entire physical universe was "caused" by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, or the expansion of the universe is "caused" by the purely hypothetical "Dark Matter" or "Dark-Energy" concepts? Or such as QM's assumed determination of any given subatomic particle or wave entity based on the direct physical interaction/s of a given subatomic "probe" element with a corresponding subatomic "target's probability wave-function", which "causes" this (assumed) "target's probability wave function" to "collapse" into a single "complimentary" "space-energy" or "mass-time" value?! The New empirically validated "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm completely negated such basic "Material-Causal" assumption – e.g., due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any single- or multiple- UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Therefore, the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm advanced our new (higher) understanding wherein the only manner in which this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) continuously "originates", "sustains", ("dissolves") and "develops" the entire physical universe is based upon its "pre-planned" Blueprint Plan of "steering" the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state of the entire physical universe in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCP as the sole reality behind the universe (e.g., and also transcending its existence); which will also include Humanity's recognition of this singular higher-ordered UCR's "sublime" characteristics of "Morality", "All-Goodness", "Peace" & "Harmony" which will therefore also characterize Humanity's "peaceful", "meaningful" and "harmonious" ("goodwill") existence!

The "robustness" of any given Scientific Theory, i.e., and especially the discovery and empirical validation of a New Scientific Paradigm (NSP) in any given discipline – far exceeds its ability (merely) to satisfy the necessary (stringent) criteria to accept this NSP, as more "valid" (and "satisfactory") than the Old Paradigm! As mentioned earlier, according to Thomas Kuhn's (1962) famous (and well-accepted) analysis of the "Structure of Scientific Revolutions", the appearance of a "New Scientific Paradigm" (NSP) ensues the existence of basic fundamental "Paradigmatic-Crisis" of the "Old Paradigm" – in our case this is the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM, characterized by an apparent basic "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM, and this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's inability to account for the accelerated expansion of the physical universe, e.g., assumed to be "caused" by (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" which are supposed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass and energy in the universe, but which could not be detected or verified experimentally (despite two full decades of trying to do so?!)

L. "G-D's Physics' Seven-Months' Challenge" to Validate It's "UNCIARE-JRH" Unique "Critical Prediction"!

Thus, Science has reached a "pivotal turning point", in which the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm has been shown to be more valid than the Old "Material-Causal-Random" Paradigm underlying both General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM), based on the direct empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" two (abovementioned unique) "Critical Predictions" pertaining to the UNCIARE (JRH) associated with the "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" ("**Hubble Tension**" otherwise "unexplained") phenomenon; and the "Proton Radius Puzzle" findings – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM! Moreover, as indicated (above), "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm was also shown capable of resolving the to provide a great advancement of our basic understanding of the physical reality brought about through its (first of its kind) complete

unification of the Four basic Physical Features (as well as between the Four fundamental Forces, as shown previously), as well as offer a satisfactory resolution of the (otherwise "unresolved") Gravitational Enigma"!

In addition to these major advancements in Twenty-First Century Physics basic understanding of the universe stemming from these growing empirical and theoretical evidences for "G-D's Physics" as the New (satisfactory) Scientific Paradigm for 21st Century Physics; "G-D's Physics" is now seeking for the "Next Eddington's" to further validate a few additional (unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm that differentiate it from the corresponding predictions of the Old MCR's Paradigm's GRT & QM! **Hence, I am calling leading Theoretical Physicists, Astronomers and Experimental Physicists (all over the world) to collaborate with him in satisfying "G-D's Physics' Seven Months Challenge!" to directly validate the "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH predicted increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion beginning during the upcoming Jewish Rosh Hashanah's two days' time interval: from October 3rd- 4th, 2024 and onwards – which should be measured as a higher rate of the universe's expansion than the rate of the universe's expansion measured until October 2nd, 2024! Direct communication regarding scientific collaboration for meeting this "G-D's Physics Seven Months' Challenge" should be directed to my personal e-mail: drbentwich@gmail.com**!

it is important to point out another (direct) empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – in continuation to the already validated UNCIARE unique Critical Prediction: As mentioned above, the UNCIARE Critical Prediction's empirical validation denotes that the universe's rate of expansion has increased from its early stage "Background Radiation" Cosmological measures to the current Astronomical indices of its contemporary rate of expansion! As noted, this result confirms "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE Critical Prediction wherein the universe's accelerated rate of expansion increases over time – in contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's assumption wherein the (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" is assumed to "cause" a "constant-rate" expansion of the universe (e.g., despite the abovementioned principle negation of the Old "Material-Causal" SRCS/SRNCs "flawed" computational structure which was negated by "G-D's Physics" "Computational Duality Principle", CDP)! Hence, the increase in the universe's rate of expansion over time has already been validated (as the unique UNCIARE Critical Prediction of "G-D's Physics") – but a more specific (direct) empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm can be tested based on a specific "time-sensitive" measurement of the universe's increase in its expansion rate during the two-days' special time-interval of the "Jewish Rosh-Hashanah" (JRH, New Year) which occurred in the previous year on September Oct. 3rd-4th (2024) and onwards – relative to the universe's rate of expansion prior to Oct. 3rd-4th, 2024 (which was expected to be lower than the rate of expansion from Oct. 3rd-4th (2024))!

Theoretical Basis & Actual "UNCIARE-JRH" Critical Prediction:

The theoretical basis for "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH unique "Critical Prediction" is anchored in "G-D's Physics" abovementioned USDOM – i.e., realizing that since the whole (continuous annual) expansion of the universe is critically dependent upon this Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF), which solely can bring about the "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE); therefore, it must also have been the case that from the initial stages of the universe's creation – this CHCF has to appear (almost) at the very beginning of the Universe's creation by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR! From "internal validity" considerations of "G-D's Physics" robust (and detailed) theoretical model of this singular (higher-ordered) UCP's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (THCD's) and associated "THCD's- Universal Computational Formula" (outlined above and previously), it becomes clear that:

a) In the same manner in which this singular (higher-ordered) UCP is

postulates to computes every consecutive UF's frame/s – at the "unfathomable" rate of " c^2/h " = 1.36^{50} sec!⁻¹ with clear indications wherein each of these "fifty zero's" is allocated to one of those THCD's (as depicted in Figure??);

b) With this allocation of the UCP's "fifty zero's" to two major "Groups":
1) the Six Secondary HCD's: Good-Will "חסד"; Conscious-Moral Development [CMD]: "גבורה"; UNCIARE-JRH & Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle, "תפארת"; UCP's Computed Potential Object, "נצח"; UCP's Teshuvah, "הרה", & UCP's Actual-Computed Object, "יסוד".

2) The Seventh HCD: "Infinite Ten-Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Materialization!"

a) Due to the (complete) "contingency" of the UNCIARE-JRH upon the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) it is postulated that the same contingency must have existed at the initial creation of the whole universe by this singular higher-ordered UCP!

b) Therefore, "G-D's Physics" Seven Days' Creation Model (USDOM) postulated that the whole creation of the entire physical universe occurred in a mere Seven Days' time-interval!

c) It is also suggested that the current computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s based on this singular higher-ordered UCP's Six Secondary HCD's (which compute those "fifty zero's" based on the previously outlined Gimatria's and Dynamic- Equilibrium Moral Principle etc.) – is also equivalent to the USDOM, in terms of its "division" to those two Major Groups: A. Six Secondary HCD's 7 B. Seventh UCP's "Infinite" THCD's Materialization!)

d) This "division" into the UCP's (two) "Major HCD's Groups can account for the SDCM's insistence upon the UCP's "completion" of the various "inanimate" matter, and "animate": plants, animals and human-beings by the sixth day (e.g., comprising the "Six Secondary HCD's" Group); with the seventh day of those initial SDCM dedicated to the "fulfillment" of the UCP's "Geulah Driven Development Universe" – since the creation of a human-being on the sixth day allow for the CHCF's continuous "advancement" of Humanity (and the whole universe) towards this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe! In much the same manner the current UCP's computation of every consecutive UF's frame also critically depends upon those two UCP's "Major HCD's Groups": the UCP's computation of the sixth "Actual Computed Object" ("יסוד") culminates all of the "Six Secondary HCD's" Group Gimatria's (e.g., from "1" to "46" zero's); and the "Seventh UCP's "Infinite" THCD's Materialization" Group "materializes" (or "fulfills") the UCP's computation of the next consecutive UF's frame/s (e.g., which also advances the universe towards "fulfilling" or "materializing" that "Ultimate Geulah Goal State" of Humanity and the universe!)

The inevitable conclusion from this detailed analysis of "G-D's Physics" new theoretical framework is that:

1) The Physical universe must have been created in a mere Seven Days' (e.g., USDOM) time-interval, e.g., due to the UCP's contingency upon the CHCF operation from the "onset" of the universe's creation by this singular higher-ordered UCP (alongside all of the other detailed abovementioned theoretical considerations associated with the UCP's Two Major HCD's Groups)!

2) The otherwise "unexplained" "Hubble's Tension" (e.g., also termed: the "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion", in multiple previous "G-D's Physics" articles) – is clearly explained through "G-D's Physics" CHCF postulate stipulating that this "Hubble's Tension" phenomenon is produced by an annual CHCF UNCIARE-JRH increase in the universe's rate of expansion (during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana's" two days of CHCF of the all the Jews around the world focusing on this singular higher-ordered UCP!) This means that "Hubble's Tension" is explained as a function of these two day's JRH (annual) CHCF which brings about "G-D's Physics" predicted UNCIARE-JRH!

3) Due to this complete "contingency" of the universe's UNCIARE upon

the CHCF's (postulated) JRH's two day's annual time interval; and an ("astounding") equivalence of "G-D's Physics" empirically validated New Scientific Paradigm of Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics – with the Jewish (and Chassidic) Thought (e.g., including the above mentioned Two Major HCD's Groups etc.); **it is also being postulated that this CHCF-JRH existed for the past 5784 years (of the Jewish Calendar!)**

4) Therefore, since according to "G-D's Physics" clear explanation of "Hubble's Tension", as "caused" by the UNCIARE-JRH CHCF -over the past 5784 years, "G-D's Physics" specific UNCIARE-JRH "Critical Prediction" predicts that the "UNCIARE-JRH" value of the particular increase in the universe's expansion rate is computed as:

The "Hubble's Tension" value (e.g., $73-67.4 = 5.6$) divided by those 5784 (JRH's) = 0.000968..!

5) **Therefore, I am calling Astronomers (all over the world) to directly collaborate with me in validating "G-D's Physics" "Seven Months' Challenge" to validate "G-D's Physics" predicted UNCIARE-JRH "Minute Annual Increase" (MAI) of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc that will occur on the upcoming JRH: Oct. 3rd-4th, 2024; relative to the current (approximate) "73" value km s⁻¹ Mpc (i.e., which should be measured precisely during the next seven months at a precision level of 0.00096 km s⁻¹ Mpc!) (This obviously requires a very significant increase in the Astronomical measurement accuracy to UNCIARE-JRH "Minute Annual Increase" (MAI) of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc!) In other words, "G-D's Physics" predicted UNCIARE-JRH "Critical Prediction" predicts an MAI of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc beginning on Oct. 3rd- 4th 2024 (e.g., relative to the next seven month's precise measurement of the universe's current rate of expansion) which will remain constant for the whole next Jewish Year (e.g., until 22.9.25 – in which an additional such MAI of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc will be added to the rate of the universe's expansion!)**

M. Science Must Accept "G-D's Physics" as the New Twenty-First Century Physics Paradigm!

It is therefore clear that Twenty-First Century Physics has reached a "Historic Pivotal Turning Point" (equivalent to the abovementioned "Paradigmatic-Shift" brought about by Eddington's empirical validation of Einstein's 1919 Solar Eclipse) – which necessitates Physics to accept "G-D's Physics" as the New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm, which replaces (and in fact includes) the Old "Material-Causal-Random" (MCR) Standard Paradigm's GRT & QM as (mere) "special-cases" within the broader theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" "Universal Computational Formula" (as shown above)! This is because precisely equivalent to the acceptance of Einstein's GRT as the New 20th Century Physics Paradigm based on a clear empirical proof for the validation of Einstein's unique "Critical Prediction" regarding GRT's "double-valued" Mercury's perihelion pathway around the Sun (e.g., 1.6 ARC) – as more accurate than the corresponding prediction of the Old "Newtonian Mechanics" Standard Paradigm (e.g., 0.8 ARC), which brought about the inevitable acceptance of Einstein's GRT as more valid than Newtonian Mechanics (i.e., including it as a "special-case" within the broader Relativistic New Scientific Paradigm); Likewise, the current article provides clear (direct) empirical proof for the validation of two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New Scientific Paradigm of "G-D's Physics" as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM, thereby validating "G-D's Physics" as the New (valid) Scientific Paradigm for Twenty-First Century Physics!

Moreover, based on the strong (and impressive) "internal validity" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, and its significant advancement of Physics (and Science, more generally) advancement of the "origin"- "true nature"- "sustenance" and "development" of the whole physical universe towards the "fulfillment" of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP or "Universal Consciousness Reality") "Geulah Goal Perfected" State of Humanity and the universe, it also warrants a special appreciation and acceptance – not only as the NSP of 21st Century Theoretical Physics, but perhaps even more significantly as altering Humanity's basic understanding of its "special role" – in fulfill-

ing this UCP's /UCR's pre-planned "steering" of the universe towards this "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State" of Humanity (and the universe): a state in which Science and Humanity will recognize the singularity of this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR which is characterized by those "sublime characteristics" of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony", and therefore this recognition will profoundly affect the existence and behavior of Humanity (itself)!

This is because in stark contrast to the basic "Material-Causal-Random" (MCR) assumption of the Old "MCR Standard Paradigm" of GRT & QM, which assumed that the whole origination of the entire physical universe was "caused" by an initial "random nuclear Big-Bang event" which "created" all of the "mass" and "energy", "space" and "time" of the universe; and that all of the development- and dynamics- of the whole universe – e.g., whether at the (macroscopic) Relativistic level or (microscopic) Quantum level is driven by mere "Material-Causal-Random" physical interactions: such as between certain "massive objects" which "cause" the "curvature of Space-Time" (which in turn determine the travelling pathways of these "massive objects" or other "less-massive" objects); or such as the (assumed) "collapse" of the subatomic "target's probability wave-function" based on its direct physical interaction with another corresponding subatomic "probe" element into a singular complimentary "space/energy" or "mass/time" value!? This Old "MCR (GRT & QM) Standard Paradigm" also assumes that the universe was created 13.77 Billions of years ago, and tries to account for the observed (but yet "unexplained") "UNCIARE" increase in the rate of the universe's expansion based on (purely hypothetical) "DM/DE" concepts (which are assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass and energy in the universe – but yet failed to be detected even after more than two decades of trying to detect those "elusive" DM/DE concepts!?) This "MCR Old Standard Paradigm" also assumes that life on our planet Earth were created and developed based on "Darwin's Natural Selection Principle" (DNSP) which was also the result of "random physical interaction/s" between certain Cosmic Rays that interacted (and "altered", i.e., "caused" certain "genetic mutations" in particular organisms which therefore could "better survive" in randomly occurring changes in their environment so that those "genetically altered" organisms could better interact, and hence "survive" and pass their genetic information to their offspring than the other "unmutated organisms" etc., as described and analyzed in previous "G-D's Physics" published articles); Hence, the whole creation of "Life" and specifically of human-beings – is assumed to have been caused by mere "Material-Causal-Random" physical interactions, i.e., with us human-beings (e.g., "homo-sapiens") assumed to have "evolved randomly" only appeared approximately 200,000 years ago! Likewise, it is assumed that the universe will "dissipate" (e.g., "disintegrate" with all of the Suns extinguished due to the Second Law of Thermodynamics, and the accelerated expansion of the universe etc.).

But, since as shown above (and previously), "G-D's Physics" "New Scientific Paradigm" has been shown to be more valid than the Old "MCR Standard Paradigm" (of GRT & QM) – in fact integrating (and unifying) between GRT & QM (e.g., as "special-cases" within the broader and more exhaustive theoretical framework) of "G-D's Physics" newly discovered singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP/UCR), and its novel computational definitions of the Four basic Physical Features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", and the new "Universal Computational Formula"; therefore we have to revise our basic understanding of the "congoing origination" of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the physical universe (as well as the entirety of the universe) – as being continuously "computed"- "dissolved"- "re-computed" and "developed" at the "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec)! thereby producing an incredibly rapid rate of "Universal Frames" (UF's) which comprise the entire physical universe (at every such "minimal time-point")! But, because "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm asserts that this singular (higher-ordered) UCP "simultaneously" computes all ex-

haustive spatial pixels in the universe (for each consecutive UF's), and that all of these exhaustive spatial pixels "dissolve" back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames; therefore, there cannot exist any "material-causal" (random) physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF's! Hence, the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm was shown to negate all of these (abovementioned) basic MCR assumptions of the Old MCR "Standard Paradigm" (e.g., including GRT's Big-Bang Model, Einstein's Equations assumed MCR relationships, QM's MCR probability wave function collapse etc., as well as DNSP's implicitly assumed MCR relationships!)

Instead, "G-D's Physics" complete unification of the Four basic Physical Features, as well as between the Four basic Forces (e.g. both – for the first time in Physics!) based on its discovery Universal Computational Formula (shown above, alongside its novel computational definitions for each of these Four basic Physical Features as being computed through the UCP's two Computational Dimensions of "Consistency" and "Framework") opens a completely new understanding of the "continuous origination", "sustenance" and "development" of the entire physical universe – as completely dependent upon- and in fact as only a "transient-phenomenal manifestation" of this singular higher-ordered UCP or UCR! Indeed, the (latter) discovery (and delineation) of this UCP's "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions", and its associated "pre-planned" "blueprint plan" for the "steering" of the universe from its initial "inanimate": "matter" through "animate": "plants", "animals", and "human-beings" – all leading and being "pre-planned" to "steer" the entire physical universe towards the fulfillment of its "Ultimate Geulah Goal" State in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize this singularity of this UCP/UCR alongside its (abovementioned) "sublime characteristics" of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" (which will therefore also characterize Humanity's behavior and existence!)

Indeed, one (of two) unique "Critical Predictions" that received direct empirical validation (in this article) is "G-D's Physics" "UNCIARE" Critical Prediction which predicted that there will be an overall increase in the universe's rate of expansion – due to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) which takes place at every "Jewish Rosh Hashanah" (two days special time interval: this year it will occur during Oct. 3rd -4th, 2024, see abovementioned "Seven Months' Challenge to Astronomers") during which time the universe's rate of expansion increases (significantly) in a "non-continuous" manner! Indeed, as shown above (and previously), this unique "UNCIARE" Critical Prediction of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm explains (satisfactorily) the (otherwise "unexplained") "Hubble Tension" increase in the universe's rate of expansion from the early Cosmological Measures to the current Astronomical Measures of the universe's expansion rate (e.g., which is closely related to the Old MCR Standard Paradigm's GRT principle inability to explain this accelerated rate of the universe's based on the purely hypothetical "DM/DE" which could not be detected experimentally for the past two decades, and moreover which could not account for such an "UNCIARE" empirically observed increase in the universe's rate of expansion over time!?) Hence, the direct empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" Predicted "UNCIARE" increase in the universe's expansion rate – due to the CHCF occurring at the JRH (as shown above) – for which there has (now) been a direct call for an even more precise "Minute Annual Increase" (MAI) of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc" (see above and previous "Seven Months Challenge to Astronomers") that is calculated based on "G-D's Physics" new (abovementioned) "Six Day Creation Model"; completely alters our basic understanding of the universe's (continuous) "origination" (by the singular higher UCP) and the centrality of the CHCF as part of UCP's "steering" of the universe towards that "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State", in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize (and accept) the singular higher-ordered reality of the UCP, alongside its (abovementioned) "sublime characteristics"

of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

N. A New Singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" – Geulah Driven Universe!

Therefore, perhaps even more significantly than the current "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "MCR Standard Paradigm" of GRT & QM to "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is Humanity (current) recognition (and acceptance) of this singular (higher-ordered) UCP's "steering" of Humanity (and the universe) towards that "Ultimate Geulah Goal", in which Humanity (and Science) accept the singularity of this UCP/UCR (which is also characterized by such "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony", and will therefore characterize also Humanity's own existence and behavior!) This means that Physics (and Science) cannot (any longer) view the physical universe based on the "glasses" of the Old "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) Paradigm of Twentieth Century's GRT or QM! We cannot (any longer) assume that the universe was created by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event (e.g., "accidentally")! This is because (as delineated and explained thoroughly previously), there could not have existed any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF's frame/s (e.g., including the negation of any such interaction between such as assumed initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event and the creation of any suns galaxies, energy or mass- in the "first", "second"... trillionth" etc. UF's frame/s!?) Likewise, we cannot assume as does GRT that the universe evolves based on direct (or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between certain "massive-objects", and their "causing" of the "curvature of Space-Time" (or conversely, the determination of the "travelling pathways" of these "massive objects" or of other "less-massive" objects as "caused" by their direct or indirect "material-causal" physical interaction/s with the assumed "curved Space-Time") – once again, because there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s; due to the simultaneity of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s (and the complete "dissolution" of all of the universe's exhaustive spatial pixels "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s back into the singularity of the UCP)!

In fact, we realize that all such exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe – merely represent a "transient-phenomenal manifestation" of this singular higher-ordered UCR, which constitutes the only true and single reality underlying (and indeed transcending) the entire physical universe! Moreover, according to "G-D's Physics" abovementioned THCD-UCF it seems that the entire development of the whole physical universe has been "pre-planned" by this singular UCP/UCR to reach the "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State" of the universe (and of Humanity)! According to this new (and profound) realization brought about by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, this singular UCR/UCP Reality has "preplanned" the whole development of the universe from "inanimate matter" through "animate": "plants", "animals", and "human-beings" to reach this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of Humanity (Science) and the universe, in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR and its "sublime characteristics" (of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!)

In fact, with the current empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" two unique (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old MCR's GRT and QM, **we now stand at a most significant "turning-point", not only for Twenty-First Century Physics (e.g., as it "crowns" and accepts "G-D's Physics" as the New satisfactory Scientific Paradigm for Twenty-First Century Physics (and Science, more generally); but even more significantly for the whole of Humanity!** This is because with the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" as the New (valid) Scientific Paradigm for Twenty-First Century – Humanity (and Science)

"enter" the beginning of this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State! This implies that with the (inevitable) acceptance of "G-D's Physics" as the New (valid) Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm, **Science allows Humanity to enter and begin the fulfillment of the universe's "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected" State, in which Humanity begins recognizing the singularity of this UCP/UCR, alongside adopting a life (and existence) that is compatible with the discovery of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) together with its "sublime characteristics" of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!**

Thus, for instance (as shown extensively previously), Humanity's recognition of the singularity of this UCR, alongside its "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" (DEMP), which teaches Humanity that this singular UCP/UCR selects one of "multiple possible future/s" – based upon each Individual human-being's moral/immoral choice/s (at every point in time), in order to "balance" (e.g., correct any immoral action/s) and "enhance" every human being's moral behavior! This implies that whenever any individual human-being ("G-d" forbid) opts to inflict pain or suffering upon another individual human-being, the UCP will select for that "offending" human-being one of "multiple possible futures", in which he/she will also have to experience the same degree of pain or suffering in order to reach a sincere state of "Teshuvah" (e.g., sincere sense of remorse and a resolute conscious decision not to repeat any such immoral action, and also trying to rectify and correct that immoral behavior towards that specific "injured" human-being...) In this manner, the UCP's utilization of this DEMP (which comprises one of its THCD's!) advances each and every Individual human-being (as well as Humanity in general!) towards the fulfillment of this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of Humanity! **We are therefore entering a unique (and "sublime") new phase in the development of Humanity (and fulfillment of the UCP's "Ultimate Geulah Goal State") in which there will be no more wars, violence, aggression etc. – on the contrary, there will prevail a sense of "Goodwill", "collaboration", "assistance" and "harmony" amongst all of Humanity, which will realize our "Oneness" with this singular "All-Goodness", "Moral", "Peaceful" and "Harmonious" UCR (alongside a deepening investigation of the true nature and characteristics of this "sublime" singular UCR)!**

Intriguingly then, "G-D's Physics" points at Humanity's (current) entering of the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" is extremely reminiscent of the Isaiah's (well-known) Prophecy: And they shall beat their swords into plowshares, and their spears into pruning hooks; nation shall not lift up sword against nation, neither shall they learn war anymore... (Isaiah 2:4) And the Great Maimonides' prophecy regarding "That time (of Geulah) there will be no hunger or war, jealousy or competition... and the whole World's preoccupation will be only to know "G-D"! (Hilchut Melachim, 12:3-5)

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